

Checklist of the lichens of Serbia

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Abstract. A list of 586 species lichenized fungi of Serbia is presented, which summarizes all records since 1859 and provides a comprehensive bibliography of sources containing Serbian records. Synonyms mainly at the species level, relevant for the Serbian records are included.

Key words: bibliography, biodiversity, fungal diversity, lichenized fungi

Introduction

During the past few decades lichenological exploration of the Mediterranean Area and Central and South-Eastern Europe area has been intensified, resulting in numerous papers on lichen diversity, inclusion of locality data in taxonomic revisions, monographs, reports on regional mycotas, and the publication of several checklists, e.g. Egea (1996), Galun & Mukhtar (1996), John (1996), Seaward (1996), Vězda & Liška (1999), Suppan *et al.* (2000), Hafellner & Türk (2001), Nimis & Martellos (2003), Bielczyk *et al.* (2004), Clerc (2004), and Mayrhofer *et al.* (2005).

This paper contributes to the investigation of the biodiversity of the Mediterranean region within the scope of the 'Commission for lichens of OPTIMA' (Organization for the Phyto-Taxonomical Investigation of the Mediterranean Area), and it is hoped that it will provide a further step towards a better understanding of the Mediterranean lichens (Nimis 1996).

Scope of the checklist

This list aims at including all species of lichenized fungi so far published from Serbia (for the area considered, see Savić *et al.*

2006: Fig. 1), together with a comprehensive bibliography of literature contributing to the knowledge of the Serbian lichen diversity.

Early publications on Serbian lichens have been published in such a way that they have been very difficult to access, and therefore virtually unknown among lichenologists (e.g. Simić 1892, 1895, and some papers by Katić). These publications were partly overlooked by Kušan (1953) in his catalogue of the lichens of Yugoslavia. In two instances we have encountered lists that have been cited in the literature, but as far as we can see have not been effectively published and only exist in a few copies not available to the public ('Gajić & Korać 1991'^{**} and 'Murati 1991'^{***}); these lists have thus not been considered in this checklist.

Furthermore, some original publications do not indicate the existence of and/or the location of voucher specimens, and some, such as the most complete work on lichens (Murati 1992, 1993), provide no locality details.

An evaluation of literature data has been carried out, and identification of earlier records with current taxonomic concepts has been attempted. This is particularly difficult for the early publications, and in the absence of voucher material it has been based on a consensus of opinion for previous usage of names as expressed in recent revisions, contemporary reports on the regional mycotas, and recent checklists. Sometimes,

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**Gajić, M. & Korać, M. (unpubl.). [A survey of lichens of Serbia]. – In: Zbornik radova, simpozijuma 'Nedeljko Košanin i botaničke nauke', Beograd-Ivanjica, 1991, pp. 394-399. (In Serbian)

***Murati, M. (unpubl.). [A contribution to the lichen flora of Serbia. II]. – In: Zbornik radova, simpozijuma 'Nedeljko Košanin i botaničke nauke', Beograd-Ivanjica, 1991, pp. 64-68. (In Serbian)

however, different opinions prevail, and synonymizations are no more than educated guesses. For particularly difficult cases, names have been cited in the section on 'Doubtful names and excluded records' below. In a few cases, however (for example regarding the recognition of *Bagliettoa*, cf. Halda 2003), a divergent position has been accepted based on our taxonomic judgement supported by unpublished data.

The distribution of the species within Serbia has not been indicated, mainly because the information is very incomplete. It has to be left for a later occasion, on the basis of a more thorough exploration of the Serbian lichens, to supplement this checklist; similarly, ecological information cannot be offered. For distribution and ecology data the reader has to consult the original records as listed under the species.

We are fully aware that in this effort to produce a checklist of the lichens of Serbia we may have overlooked some records, and encourage colleagues to contribute further data for a future edition.

Lichenological exploration of Serbia

The first records of lichens from Serbia derive from Pančić's (1859) work on the flora of serpentine areas of Central Serbia. Simić's (1892) list of 88 lichen taxa included a considerable number of crustose lichens. In further contributions on the cryptogams of Serbia (Simić 1895, 1896, 1897, 1898, 1900), he reported new lichen records, such as *Calicium adspersum*, *Collema auriforme*, *C. cristatum*, *Diploschistes actinostomus*, *Fuscidea cyathoides*, *Icmadophila ericetorum*, *Placynthiella uliginosa*, *Porpidia crustulata*, *Protopannaria pezizoides*, *Pycnothelia papillaria*, *Trapeliopsis granulosa*, *Usnea barbata*, and *Verrucaria fuscella*, for some of which there are few or no recent records. In a series of small papers, Katić (1903, 1904, 1907) recorded more species, and also mentioned those associated with vegetation studies of bogs (Katić 1910); interesting records include *Bellemerea alpina*, *Cetraria ericetorum*, *C. muricata*, *Lecidea lapicida*, *Ophioparma ventosa*, *Parmotrema chinensis*, and *Rinodina milvina*. For a short description of the early lichenological exploration of Serbia by Simić and Katić, see Ranojević (1905). A major contribution to the knowledge of the Serbian lichen biota by Szatala & Timkó (1926) was based on lichens collected by J. Andrasovszky during his trip from Belgrade to the southernmost parts of Kosovo, in the area around Peć and Kosovska Mitrovica; the paper also dealt with lichens collected in Albania. Further comprehensive contributions were published by Servít, who enumerated lichens collected by himself in 1918 (Servít 1934), from localities he, and also Kušan (1953), referred to as 'Slavonia' (Stielers Hand-Atlas 1910). Servít also published on the lichens of the Rtanj Mountains in Eastern Serbia (Servít 1935), based on material collected by Friedrich and Erwin Zimmerman in 1932. Soška (1949) contributed to the knowledge of the lichen diversity of Belgrade and surroundings.

Important collectors of lichens in Serbia during the first half of the 20th century were J. Andrasovszky (published by Szatala & Timkó in 1926, and included by Soška in 1949), Friedrich and Erwin Zimmerman (Servít 1935), Servít (1934), and Gallé (1935).

A comprehensive catalogue of the lichens of Yugoslavia by Kušan (1953) is a detailed compilation including synonymy and distribution of the species, and also describes the lichenological exploration of the area with extensive references to earlier literature since the time of Scopoli. Kušan listed 1159 species from Yugoslavia, including many species from Serbia. In comparison with other areas of Yugoslavia, like Dalmatia and other parts of Croatia and Bosnia-Herzegovina, the records from Serbia are, however, few. One reason for this is that Kušan actually overlooked some early papers (e.g. several by Simić and Katić). Kušan in this treatment details localities, collectors, year of collecting and ecological details and furthermore gives references to earlier publications. References to Kušan (1953) are also supplied for the convenience of the reader.

After a long period with lower activity in the exploration of the lichens of Serbia – the main exceptions being Krause & Klement (1958), Marinović & Bata (1967), Marinović & Stanković (1972), and Gallé (1966, 1974, 1975) – further contributions were published again in the 1980s and much more frequently in the 1990s. New lichen records for Serbia during the 1980s were included in Tatić & Veljović (1982), Bejtullahu *et al.* (1983), and Gajić (1983, 1986, 1988, 1989).

An important further step was reached with the publication of a lichen 'flora' in two parts by Murati (1992, 1993). This contributed substantially to our knowledge of the lichens of the former Yugoslavia, particularly by including information from the international lichenological literature published after Kušan (1953), and by supplying keys to the species. His records of species new to Serbia are, however, neither connected to specific localities nor to voucher specimens, but have nevertheless been accepted in this checklist. A summary of lichen diversity in Serbia and Montenegro, and a comparison of the lichen diversity of these regions, was supplied by Savić (1995), who at the time estimated the number of lichen species in Serbia to be 406.

Lately, further additions were included in papers by Milić & Blaženčić (1993), Cvijan *et al.* (1995), Randelović & Kujundžić (1995), Stamenković (1995, 1998), Savić (1996, 1998), Zlatković & Randelović (1996), Szabados (1998), and Todorović (1998). In the early 21st century Dimović (2001, 2003), Kojić (2002), Dimović & Lökös (2003), Seaward & John (2005), and Savić *et al.* (2006) added further species.

Records in the checklist

Here we report 586 species from Serbia. They are listed alphabetically, with accepted names given in bold, often followed by synonyms in italics. The synonymy is incomplete,

including only synonyms used in published sources. The records are ordered chronologically within parantheses, with reference to publication (including page reference) and, if the accepted name has not been used, followed by the synonymous name used in the publication. Synonymizations are in accordance with opinions provided in several recent checklists and revisions, but they are also a consequence of our opinions on generic delimitations. If incongruences with nomenclaturally correct author citations occur, or if we have not been able to find the name referred to, the name used in the publication is indicated within quotation marks, and represent our interpretations. In some other cases identifications of published names with currently accepted names is uncertain and are, at best, educated guesses; this is particular true of names that have been widely used in a way not consistent with the type material, i.e. the names followed by 'auct.'

Infraspecific taxa have generally not been included; only infraspecific taxa which are generally considered to represent distinct species have been included in the lists of synonymy – except for in *Melanelia fuliginosa*. Infraspecific names have also been included within quotation marks when they are not nomenclaturally correct and/or when we have not been able to trace them. In a few cases where the confusion is thorough – or when we have been unable to interpret or trace names – the records have been cited under 'Doubtful names and excluded records'.

Lichenized fungi

- Acarospora cervina* A. Massal. (Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 99)
- Acarospora fuscata* (Schrad.) Th. Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167; Magnusson 1929: 299; Servít 1935: 77; Kušan 1936: 187, 1953: 331; Murati 1992: 69; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Acarospora glaucocarpa* (Ach.) Körb. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167; Magnusson 1929: 237; Servít 1934: 140; Kušan 1953: 329; Murati 1992: 70; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Acarospora macrospora* (Hepp) A. Massal ex Bagl. (Magnusson 1935-1936: 264; Servít 1935: 77; Kušan 1953: 332; Murati 1990: 47, 1992: 70)
- Acarospora peliscypha* Th. Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167; Kušan 1953: 331; Murati 1992: 73)
- Acarospora veronensis* A. Massal. (Servít 1935: 77; Kušan 1953: 329; Gallé 1975: 292; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Murati 1990: 47, 1992: 75; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Acrocordia conoidea* (Fr.) Körb. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Acrocordia gemmata* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Simić 1892: 453, 1895: 137; Servít 1934: 124 as *Arthopyrenia alba*, 1935: 74 as *A. alba*; Kušan 1953: 86-87 as *A. alba*; Murati 1990: 48, 1992: 77)
- Agonimia gelatinosa* (Ach.) Brand & Diederich (Murati 1993: 197 as *Polyblastia gelatinosa*)
- Alectoria ochroleuca* (Hoffm.) A. Massal. (Dimović 2003: 144)
- Alectoria sarmentosa* (Ach.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174; Kušan 1953: 474****; Murati 1990: 48, 1992: 79)
- Amandinea punctata* (Hoffm.) Coppins & Scheid. (Simić 1897: 7 as *Buellia myriocarpa*; Gallé 1935: 270 as *B. myriocarpa*, 1975: 295 as *Buellia punctiformis*; Servít 1934: 157 as *Buellia punctata*, 1935: 85 as *B. punctata*; Kušan 1953: 547-548 as *B. punctata*; Murati 1990: 48 as *B. punctata*, 1992: 138 as *B. punctata*; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *B. punctata*; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *B. punctata*; Randelović 1995: 20 as *B. punctata*; Stamenković 1995: 43 as *B. punctata*, 1998: 72 as *B. punctata*; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 59 as *B. punctata*; Todorović 1998: 75 as *B. punctata*; Dimović 2001: 108 as *B. punctata*, 2003: 144 as *B. punctata*; Kojić 2002: 144 as *B. punctata*; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Anaptychia ciliaris* (L.) Körb. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 116 & 146, 1896: 9, 1898: 15, 1900: 47; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 179; Gallé 1935: 272, 1975: 296; Servít 1934: 160, 1935: 86; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 583-584; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 112; Gajić 1983: 40; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66; Murati 1992: 81; Kojić 2002: 144; Dimović 2003: 144)
- Anaptychia crinalis* (Schleich.) Vězda (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 179 as *A. ciliaris* var. *crinalis*; Servít 1934: 160 as *A. ciliaris* var. *crinalis*, 1935: 86 as '*A. ciliaris* f. *crinalis*'; Kušan 1953: 584-585 as *A. ciliaris* var. *crinalis*; Gallé 1975: 296 as *A. ciliaris* var. *crinalis*; Murati 1992: 82)
- Anema decipiens* (A. Massal.) Forssell (Servít 1934: 129; Kušan 1953: 153; Murati 1992: 83)
- Arthonia dispersa* (Schrad.) Nyl. (Servít 1934: 126; Gallé 1935: 265, 1975: 291; Kušan 1953: 108; Murati 1992: 87; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Arthonia punctiformis* Ach. (Simić 1892: 453, 1895: 134; Gallé 1935: 266, 1975: 291; Murati 1992: 89)
- Arthonia radiata* (Pers.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 453 as *A. vulgaris*, 1895: 134 as *A. vulgaris*; Servít 1934: 126, 1935: 75; Soška 1949: 109 as *A. vulgaris*; Kušan 1953: 111-112; Gallé 1975: 291 as 'var. *astroidea* Mudd & var. *schwartziana* Sydow'; Murati 1992: 90; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Arthonia ruana* A. Massal. (Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *Arthothelium ruanum*)

****This record is based on material collected by Andrasovszky (Szatala & Timkó 1926) and referred to *A. sarmentosa* on p. 174. It was re-determined by Gyelnik (1932: 50) to *Alectoria degenii* Szat., which is a synonym of *Bryoria capillaris*.

- Arthopyrenia analepta* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 125 as *A. fallax*; Kušan 1953: 83 as *A. fallax*; Murati 1992: 96 as *A. lapponina*; Szabados 1998: 59)
- Arthopyrenia cinereo-pruinosa* (Schaer.) A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 124; Kušan 1953: 84; Murati 1992: 95)
- Arthopyrenia inconspicua* J. Lahm (Servít 1934: 125; Kušan 1953: 83; Murati 1992: 96)
- Arthopyrenia stenospora* Körb. (Servít 1934: 125; Kušan 1953: 81)
- Arthothelium sardoum* Bagl. (Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178)
- Arthothelium spectabile* Flot. ex A. Massal. (Katić 1904: 4)
- Arthrosporum populorum* A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 139 as *Bacidia acclinis*; Kušan 1953: 258 as *B. acclinis*; Murati 1992: 120 as *Bacidia populorum*)
- Aspicilia caesiocinerea* (Nyl. ex Malbr.) Arnold (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Aspicilia gibbosa* Ach. α *vulgaris* Körb.', 1895: 127 as '*A. gibbosa* Ach. '; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as *Lecanora gibbosa*; Kušan 1936: 189, 1953: 364 as *L. gibbosa*; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Murati 1992: 106 as '*A. gibbosa*'; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Aspicilia calcarea* (L.) Mudd (Simić 1892: 452 as '*A. contorta* Flörke. α *calcarea* L.', 1895: 127; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as '*Lecanora calcarea* v. *concreta* f. *ochracea*'; Servít 1935: 78 as *Lecanora calcarea*; Kušan 1936: 188, 1953: 356-357 as *L. calcarea*; Murati 1992: 103; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Kojić 2002: 144; Dimović 2003: 144)
- Aspicilia cinerea* (L.) Körb. (Simić 1892: 452 as '*A. cinerea* L. α *vulgaris* Körb.', 1895: 127; Katić 1907: 14, 1910: 39 as '*Lecanora (Aspicilia) cinerea*'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as *Lecanora cinerea*; Szatala 1931: 136; Servít 1935: 78 as *L. cinerea*; Kušan 1953: 358-359 as *L. cinerea*; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Murati 1992: 103; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Aspicilia contorta* (Hoffm.) Kremp. (Servít 1934: 140 as *Lecanora contorta*, 1935: 78 as '*L. contorta* v. *cinereovirens*'; Kušan 1953: 360-361 as *L. contorta*; Murati 1992: 105; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Aspicilia farinosa* (Flörke) Arnold (Katić 1910: 39 as '*Lecanora farinosa* Ach. '; Servít 1935: 78 as *L. farinosa*; Kušan 1953: 363 as *L. farinosa*; Murati 1992: 106)
- Aspicilia hoffmannii* auct. (Servít 1935: 78 as *Lecanora hoffmannii*; Kušan 1953: 364 as *L. hoffmannii*; Murati 1992: 107; Seaward & John 2005: 66 as *A. contorta* subsp. *hoffmanniana*)
- Aspicilia laevata* (Ach.) Arnold (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as *Lecanora laevata*; Kušan 1953: 365 as *L. laevata*; Murati 1992: 108)
- Aspicilia moenium* (Vain.) G. Thor & Timdal (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Aspicilia polychroma* Anzi (Krause & Klement 1958: 6)
- Aspicilia serpentimicola* (Suza) Räsänen (Murati 1990: 48)
- Aspicilia viridescens* (A. Massal.) Hue (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as *Lecanora viridescens*; Kušan 1953: 369 as *L. viridescens*; Murati 1992: 110)
- Bacidia bagliettoana* (A. Massal. & De Not.) Jatta (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Bilimbia sphaeroides* Sommerf. α *muscorum* Sw. '; Servít 1934: 139 as *Bacidia muscorum*; Kušan 1953: 267 as *B. muscorum*; Murati 1992: 116)
- Bacidia friesiana* (Hepp) Körb. (Servít 1934: 139; Kušan 1953: 265; Murati 1992: 117)
- Bacidia herbarum* (Stitzenb.) Arnold (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Bacidia rubella* (Hoffm.) A. Massal. (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 130, 1900: 47; Katić 1904: 4; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165; Servít 1934: 139 as *B. luteola*, 1935: 76 as *B. luteola*; Soška 1949: 109; Kušan 1953: 266 as *B. luteola*; Murati 1990: 48, 1992: 120; Szabados 1998: 59)
- Bacidia subincompta* (Nyl.) Arnold (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Bacidia trachona* (Ach.) Lettau (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Bacidia vermifera* (Nyl.) Th. Fr. (Szabados 1998: 59 as *B. hegetschweileri*)
- Bagliettoa baldensis* (A. Massal.) Vězda (Servít 1936: 258 as *Verrucaria serbica*, 1939: 132 as *Verrucaria baldensis* var. *serbica*; Kušan 1953: 34 as *V. baldensis*; Gajić 1988: 67 as *V. baldensis* var. *serbica*; Murati 1993: 260 as *V. baldensis*)
- Bagliettoa parmigera* (J. Steiner) Vězda & Poelt (Servít 1935: 74 as *Verrucaria parmigera*; Kušan 1953: 36 as *V. parmigera*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Bagliettoa parmigerella* (Zahlbr.) Vězda & Poelt (Murati 1993: 269 as *Verrucaria parmigerella*)
- Bagliettoa steineri* (Kušan) Vězda (Servít 1935: 74 as *Verrucaria steineri*; Kušan 1953: 32; Murati 1993: 271 as *V. steineri*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Bellemerea alpina* (Sommerf.) Clauzade & Cl. Roux (Katić 1910: 39 as *Lecanora alpina*)
- Bellemerea cinereorufescens* (Ach.) Clauzade & Cl. Roux (Murati 1992: 104)
- Biatorella hemisphaerica* Anzi (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Bilimbia lobulata* (Sommerf.) Hafellner & Coppins (Murati 1990: 51 as *Toninia lobulata*)
- Bilimbia sabuletorum* (Schreb.) Arnold (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Lecidella sabuletorum* (Schreb.)', 1895: 131 as '*Lecidella sabuletorum* (Schreb.)'; Katić 1907: 14 as '*Lecidella sabuletorum* (Schreb.)'; Servít 1934: 139 as '*Bacidia sabuletorum* f. *ludens*'; Kušan 1953: 262 as *B. sabuletorum*; Murati 1992: 121 as *Mycobilimbia sabuletorum*)
- Brodoa intestiniformis* (Vill.) Goward (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
- Bryoria capillaris* (Ach.) Brodo & D. Hawksw. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174 as *Alectoria implexa*; Gyelnik 1932: 50 as *Alectoria degenii*; Kušan 1934: 65 as *Alectoria jubata* var. *implexa*, 1953: 472 as *A. jubata* var. *implexa*, 474 as '*Alectoria sarmentosa* ... sub *A. degenii*'; Dimović 2003: 144)

- Bryoria chalybeiformis* (L.) Brodo & D. Hawksw. (Katić 1907: 12 as '*Bryopogon jubatum* Link. var. *chalibeiforme*'; Kušan 1953: 473 as '*Alectoria jubata* f. *chalybeiformis*')
Bryoria fuscescens (Gyeln.) Brodo & D. Hawksw. (Simić 1892: 450 as '*Bryopogon jubatum* L. α *prolixium*' Ach., 1895: 114 as *B. jubatum*; Katić 1907: 12 as '*Bryopogon jubatum* Link.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174 as *Alectoria jubata* var. *prolixa*; Kušan 1953: 472-473 as *A. jubata*, *A. jubata* var. *prolixa*; Murati 1990: 48, 1992: 129 & 131 as *Bryoria prolixa*; Savić 1996: 56 as *B. jubata*)
Bryoria implexa (Hoffm.) Brodo & D. Hawksw. (Murati 1992: 128)
- Buellia aethalea* (Ach.) Th. Fr. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
Buellia badia (Fr.) A. Massal. (Servít 1935: 85; Kušan 1953: 554; Murati 1990: 48, 1992: 135; Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
Buellia disciformis (Fr.) Mudd (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Kušan 1953: 545; Murati 1992: 136)
Buellia erubescens Arnold (Murati 1990: 48 as *B. zahlbruckneri*, 1992: 140 as *B. zahlbruckneri*)
Buellia griseovirens (Turner & Borrer ex Sm.) Almb. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 100)
Buellia schaeveri De Not. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Kušan 1953: 549; Murati 1992: 139)
Buellia spuria (Schaer.) Anzi (Krause & Klement 1958: 7)
- Calicium adpersum* Pers. (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 132; Kušan 1953: 103; Murati 1993: 74)
Calicium glaucellum Ach. (Murati 1990: 48)
Calicium trabinellum (Ach.) Ach. (Murati 1990: 48)
Calicium viride Pers. (Murati 1990: 48; Dimović 2003: 144)
- Caloplaca alociza* (A. Massal.) Mig. (Servít 1935: 81 as '*Blastenia agardhiana* f. *albopruinosa*'; Kušan 1953: 502 as *C. agardhiana* f. *albopruinosa*; Murati 1993: 85; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca ammiospila (Wahlenb.) H. Olivier (Murati 1990: 48 as *C. cinnamomea*, 1993: 88 as *C. cinnamomea*)
Caloplaca aractina (Fr.) Håyren (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176 as *C. fuscoatra*; Servít 1935: 85 as *C. viridirufa*; Kušan 1953: 527 as *C. viridirufa*; Murati 1993: 85)
Caloplaca aurantia (Pers.) Hellb. (Servít 1934: 156 as *C. callopsima*, 1935: 81; Kušan 1953: 531-532 as '*C. aurantia* v. *dalmatica*', 533 as *C. callopsima*; Gallé 1975: 294; Murati 1993: 86)
Caloplaca cerina (Ehrh. ex Hedw.) Th. Fr. (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Callopsima cerinum* α *ehrharti* Schaer.', 1895: 124 as *C. cerinum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175 as *C. gilva*, 175 as *C. cerina* var. *muscorum*; Servít 1934: 154, 1935: 81; Gallé 1935: 269 as *C. gilva*, 1975: 294; Kušan 1953: 506; Murati 1990: 48, 1993: 87; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72)
Caloplaca cerinella (Nyl.) Flagey (Savić 1998: 339; Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
Caloplaca cerinelloides (Erichsen) Poelt (Servít 1934: 156; Kušan 1953: 522 as '*C. pyracea* f. *cerinelloides*')
Caloplaca chalybaea (Fr.) Müll. Arg. (Servít 1935: 81; Kušan 1953: 509; Murati 1993: 88; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca chrysodeta (Vain. ex Räsänen) Dombr. (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca cirrochroa (Ach.) Th. Fr. (Servít 1934: 156, 1935: 82; Kušan 1953: 534; Gallé 1975: 294 as *Gasparrinia cirrochroa*; Murati 1993: 89)
Caloplaca citrina (Hoffm.) Th. Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176; Gallé 1935: 269, 1966: 30, 1974: 38, 1975: 294; Kušan 1953: 510; Murati 1993: 89; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
Caloplaca coronata (Kremp. ex Körb.) J. Steiner (Servít 1935: 82; Kušan 1953: 510; Murati 1993: 90)
Caloplaca crenularia (With.) J.R. Laundon (Krause & Klement 1958: 6; Murati 1990: 48 as *C. festiva*; Murati 1993: 90; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca crenulatella (Nyl.) H. Olivier (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca decipiens (Arnold) Blomb. & Forssell (Gallé 1935: 269, 1966: 29-30, 1974: 38 as *Gasparrinia decipiens*, 1975: 294 as *G. decipiens*; Murati 1993: 91; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
Caloplaca demissa (Körb.) Arup & Grube (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 129 as *Lecanora demissa*; Servít 1935: 78 as *Lecanora incusa*; Kušan 1953: 402 as *L. incusa*; Murati 1991: 65 as *L. demissa*, 1993: 137 as *L. demissa*).
Caloplaca ferruginea (Huds.) Th. Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174; Kušan 1953: 512; Gallé 1975: 294; Murati 1993: 92)
Caloplava festivella (Nyl.) Kieff. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca flavescens (Huds.) J.R. Laundon (Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20 as *C. heppiana*)
Caloplaca flavorubescens (Huds.) J.R. Laundon (Simić 1897: 7 as '*Callopsima aurantiacum* (Lightf.) v. *rubescens* Ach.>'; Murati 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *Caloplaca aurantiaca*; Todorović 1998: 75 as *C. aurantiaca*)
Caloplaca granulosa (Müll. Arg.) Jatta (Servít 1935: 82; Kušan 1953: 535; Murati 1993: 92)
Caloplaca grimmiae (Nyl.) H. Olivier (Servít 1935: 82; Kušan 1953: 514; Poelt 1975: 429 as *C. congregiatus*; Poelt & Kalb 1985: 132; Murati 1993: 93; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca haematites (St.-Amans) Zwackh (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176; Kušan 1953: 515; Murati 1993: 93)
Caloplaca herbidella (Hue) H. Magn. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca holocarpa (Hoffm. ex Ach.) A.E. Wade (Servít 1934: 155 as *C. pyracea*; Gallé 1935: 269 as *C. pyracea*, 1974: 38 as *C. pyracea*, 1975: 294 as *C. pyracea*; Kušan 1953: 522 as *C. pyracea*; Murati 1993: 94; Seaward & John 2005: 66 as *C. lithophila*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca inconnexa (Nyl.) Zahlbr. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
Caloplaca irrubescens (Arnold) Zahlbr. (Murati 1993: 94)

- Caloplaca jungermanniae* (Vahl) Th. Fr. (Murati 1990: 48, 1993: 94)
- Caloplaca lactea* (A. Massal.) Zahlbr. (Servít 1934: 154, 1935: 83; Kušan 1936: 198, 1953: 515; Murati 1993: 95; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Caloplaca lobulata* (Flörke) Hellb. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176; Gallé 1935: 270 as *Xanthoria lobulata*, 1975: 294 as *X. lobulata*; Kušan 1953: 535; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 330; Murati 1992: 376 as *C. boulyi*)
- Caloplaca luteoalba* (Turner) Th. Fr. (Simić 1892: 452 as *Calloporisma luteoalbum*, 1895: 124 as *C. luteoalbum*; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Caloplaca obliterans* (Nyl.) Blomb. & Forssell (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Caloplaca ochracea* (Schaer.) Flagey (Servít 1935: 81 as *Xanthocarpia ochracea*; Kušan 1953: 499 as *Blastenia ochracea*)
- Caloplaca rubelliana* Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176; Kušan 1953: 523; Murati 1993: 96)
- Caloplaca saxicola* (Hoffm.) Nordin (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Amphiloma murorum* Hoffm. var. *vulgare*', 1895: 123 as *A. murorum*; Katić 1910: 39 as '*C. murorum*'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176 as *C. murorum*; Gallé 1935: 270 as *Placodium murorum*, 1966: 29-30 as *C. murorum*, 1975: 294 as *Gasparrinia murorum*; Soška 1949: 111 as '*C. murorum*'; Kušan 1953: 536 as *C. murorum*; Murati 1993: 97)
- Caloplaca saxifragarum* Poelt (Murati 1993: 97)
- Caloplaca teicholyta* (Ach.) J. Steiner (Gallé 1974: 38, 1975: 294; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Caloplaca tiroliensis* Zahlbr. (Murati 1990: 49, 1993: 98)
- Caloplaca variabilis* (Pers.) Müll. Arg. (Kušan 1936: 198, 1953: 525; Murati 1993: 99; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20)
- Caloplaca velana* (A. Massal.) Du Rietz (Servít 1935: 84; Kušan 1953: 519 as *C. placidia*; Murati 1993: 99; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Seaward & John 2005: 66 as *C. dolomiticola*)
- Candelaria concolor* (Dicks.) Stein (Simić 1895: 146 as *C. vulgaris*; Gallé 1935: 268, 1975: 293; Servít 1934: 145; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 425; Murati 1992: 141; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 144)
- Candelariella aurella* (Hoffm.) Zahlbr. (Gallé 1935: 267 as '*Candelariella subsimilis* Th. Fr.', 1975: 292; Servít 1935: 80; Kušan 1953: 422; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 142; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Savić 1998: 339; Kojić 2002: 144; Dimović 2003: 144; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Candelariella coralliza* (Nyl.) H. Magn. (Dimović 2003: 144)
- Candelariella medians* (Nyl.) A.L. Sm. (Servít 1934: 145 as '*Candelariella granulosa*'; Kušan 1953: 425 as *C. granulata*; Murati 1992: 143)
- Candelariella reflexa* (Nyl.) Lettau (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Candelariella vitellina* (Hoffm.) Müll. Arg. (Simić 1897: 7 as '*Calloporisma vitellinum* (Ehrh.)'; Katić 1910: 39; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170; Gallé 1935: 267, 1974: 39, 1975: 293; Servít 1935: 80; Rudski 1949: 61; Kušan 1953: 423; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Poelt 1975: 429; Murati 1992: 143; Stamenković 1995: 43; Savić 1996: 56, 1998: 339; Szabados 1998: 59; Kojić 2002: 144; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Candelariella xanthostigma* (Ach.) Lettau (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170; Servít 1934: 145, 1935: 80; Kušan 1936: 192 as *C. vitellina* var. *xanthostigma*, 1953: 424 as *C. vitellina* var. *xanthostigma*; Gallé 1975: 292; Murati 1992: 144; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 59; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Catapyrenium cinereum* (Pers.) Körb. (Murati 1990: 48)
- Catillaria lenticularis* (Ach.) Th. Fr. (Murati 1990: 49; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Catillaria nigroclavata* (Nyl.) Schuler (Servít 1934: 138; Kušan 1953: 254; Murati 1992: 152)
- Cetraria aculeata* (Schreb.) Fr. (Simić 1898: 15 as *Cornicularia aculeata*; Murati 1992: 180 as *Coelocaulon aculeatum*; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 68 as *Coelocaulon aculeatum*)
- Cetraria ericetorum* Opiz (Katić 1907: 13 as *C. islandica* var. *crispa*, 1910: 39 as *C. islandica* var. *crispa*; Kušan 1953: 467 as *C. islandica* var. *tenuifolia*; Murati 1992: 156)
- Cetraria islandica* (L.) Ach. (Simić 1895: 116, 1898: 15; Kušan 1930: 4, 1953: 466; Rudski 1949: 61; Mišić *et al.* 1978: 219, 295, 313, 332 & 338; Gajić 1989: 96; Murati 1992: 156; Savić 1996: 57; Dimović 2003: 144)
- Cetraria muricata* (Ach.) Eckfeldt (Katić 1907: 12 as '*Cornicularia aculeata* Schreb. var. *alpina* Schaer.', 1910: 39 as '*Cornicularia aculeata* Schreb. var. *alpina* Schaer.'; Kušan 1953: 475 as '*Cornicularia tenuissima* v. *alpina*')
- Cetrelia cetrarioides* (Delise ex Duby) W.L. Culb. & C.F. Culb. (Gallé 1935: 268 as *Parmelia cetrarioides*, 1975: 293)
- Cetrelia olivetorum* (Nyl.) W.L. Culb. & C.F. Culb. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 173 as *Parmelia olivaria*; Kušan 1953: 461 as *P. olivaria*; Murati 1992: 158; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Chaenotheca chrysocephala* (Turner ex Ach.) Th. Fr. (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Chaenotheca furfuracea* (L.) Tibell (Simić 1892: 453 as '*Coniocybe furfuracea* α *vulgaris* Schaer.', 1895: 133 as *C. furfuracea*; Servít 1934: 126 as *C. furfuracea*; Kušan 1953: 104 – misplaced under *Coniocybe hyalinella*; Murati 1990: 49 as *C. furfuracea*, 1993: 103)
- Chaenotheca xyloxena* Nádv. (Murati 1990: 48 as *C. nudiuscula*)

- Chrysothrix candelaris* (L.) J.R. Laundon (Gallé 1975: 296 as *Lepraria candelaris*; Murati 1993: 107; Savić 1998: 339)
- Chrysothrix chlorina* (Ach.) J.R. Laundon (Murati 1993: 107)
- Cladonia chlorophaea* (Flörke ex Sommerf.) Spreng. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166 as *C. pyxidata* var. *chlorophaea*; Soška 1949: 110; Servít 1934: 139, 1935: 77; Kušan 1953: 310; Gallé 1975: 291; Murati 1992: 167; Savić 1996: 57; Dimović 2003: 144)
- Cladonia coccifera* (L.) Willd. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Cladonia coniocraea* (Flörke) Spreng. (Gallé 1935: 266, 1975: 291 as 'f. *ceratodes* (Flörke.) Anders'; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Savić 1998: 339; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Cladonia convoluta* (Lam.) Anders (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *C. foliacea* var. *convoluta*; Rudski 1949: 61 as *C. endiviaefolia*; Soška 1949: 110 as *C. endiviaefolia*; Kušan 1953: 317 as *C. foliacea* var. *convoluta*; Gallé 1975: 291; Murati 1992: 167; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 144; Kojić 2002: 143; Litterski & Ahti 2004: 211)
- Cladonia cornuta* (L.) Hoffm. (Dimović 2003: 144)
- Cladonia crispata* (Ach.) Flot. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166; Kušan 1953: 300; Murati 1992: 168; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 144)
- Cladonia deformis* (L.) Hoffm. (Savić 1996: 57)
- Cladonia digitata* (L.) Hoffm. (Simić 1895: 112; Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Cladonia fimbriata* (L.) Fr. (Simić 1892: 450 as 'α *vulgaris*', 1895: 112 & 145, 1900: 47; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167; Servít 1934: 139; Gallé 1935: 266 as *C. minor*, 1975: 291 as 'var. *simplex* (Weis.) Flot., f. *minor* (K. G. Hagen) Vain., f. *conista* (L.) Arn.', *C. major*; Soška 1949: 110; Kušan 1953: 311; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111; Murati 1992: 169; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *C. minor*; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Savić 1998: 339; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 144; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Cladonia foliacea* (Huds.) Willd. (Simić 1892: 450 as *C. alcicornis*, 1895: 111 & 145 as *C. alcicornis*, 1897: 6 as *C. alcicornis*; Gajić 1986: 52; Murati 1992: 170; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 68; Savić 1996: 57; Dimović 2001: 109)
- Cladonia furcata* (Huds.) Schrad. (Simić 1892: 451 as 'f. *racemosa* Wahlb.', 1895: 112 & 145 as f. *racemosa*; Katić 1910: 40 as '*C. furcata* Fr. var. *racemosa* Flörke. f. *squamulosa* Schaer.'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166; Rudski 1949: 61; Gallé 1975: 291 as 'var. *pinnata*, f. *abbreviata* Scriba, f. *foliosa* Flörke., var. *racemosa* (Hoffm.) Flörke'; Gajić 1986: 52; Murati 1990: 49 as var. *pinnata*; Murati 1992: 171; Savić 1996: 57 as 'var. *pinnata* (Flk) Vain.'; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 144; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Cladonia gracilis* (L.) Willd. (Dimović 2003: 144; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Cladonia macilenta* Hoffm. (Servít 1934: 139 as *C. bacillaris*; Kušan 1953: 290 as *C. bacillaris*; Gajić 1986: 52 as *C. bacillaris*; Murati 1992: 165 as *C. bacillaris*)
- Cladonia magyarica* Vain. (Gallé 1975: 291 as f. *carpophora* Gallé, 'f. *foliosissima* Gallé', f. *prolifera* Gallé, f. *truncata* Gallé)
- Cladonia ochrochlora* Flörke (Servít 1934: 139; Savić 1996: 57)
- Cladonia parasitica* (Hoffm.) Hoffm. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166 as *C. delicata*; Kušan 1953: 302 as *C. delicata*; Murati 1992: 173)
- Cladonia phyllophora* Hoffm. (Simić 1892: 450 as 'C. *degenerans* α *vulgaris*', 1895: 112 as *C. degenerans*; Kušan 1953: 304 as *C. degenerans*; Gallé 1975: 291 as 'C. *degenerans* f. *euphorea* (Ach.) Vain.'; Gajić 1986: 52 as *C. degenerans*; Murati 1992: 174)
- Cladonia pleurota* (Flörke) Schaer. (Dimović 2003: 144)
- Cladonia pocillum* (Ach.) Grognot (Simić 1895: 145 as *C. pyxidata* var. *pocillum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *C. pyxidata* var. *pocillum*; Kušan 1953: 308 as *C. pyxidata* var. *pocillum*; Gallé 1975: 291 as *C. pyxidata* var. *pocillum*)
- Cladonia pyxidata* (L.) Hoffm. (Simić 1892: 450 as 'C. *pyxidata* α *neglecta* Flörke', 1895: 112; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166 as 'C. *pyxidata* v. *neglecta*'; Kušan 1953: 307; Soška 1949: 110; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111; Gajić 1986: 52, 1988; Murati 1990: 49; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66; Murati 1992: 175; Savić 1996: 57; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 144)
- Cladonia rangiferina* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Simić 1892: 451 as 'α *vulgaris* Schaer.'; Rudski 1949: 61; Soška 1949: 110; Mišić *et al.* 1978: 220, 313 & 340; Gajić 1988: 68; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 68)
- Cladonia rangiformis* Hoffm. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166; Kušan 1953: 298; Gallé 1975: 291; Murati 1992: 175; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 68; Litterski & Ahti 2004: 216; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Cladonia rei* Schaer. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Cladonia squamosa* Hoffm. (Simić 1892: 451 as 'α *ventricosa* Fr.', 1895: 112; Soška 1949: 110; Kušan 1953: 301; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111; Gajić 1983: 39; Murati 1992: 176; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 145)
- Cladonia subrangiformis* Sandst. (Gallé 1975: 291)
- Cladonia subulata* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Gallé 1975: 291 as 'C. *cornutoradiata* (Coem.) Zopf. f. *furcellata* (Hoffm.) Vain., f. *radiata* (Schreb.) Sandst.'; Murati 1992: 176)
- Cladonia uncialis* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)

Note: Indicated as possibly '?' occurring in Serbia by Litterski & Ahti (2004: 219).

Clauzadea immersa (Hoffm.) Hafellner & Bellem. (Servít 1935: 81 as *Protoblastenia immersa*; Kušan 1953: 491 as *P. immersa*; Murati 1992: 312; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)

- Clauzadea monticola* (Schaer.) Hafellner & Bellem. (Servit 1934: 148 as *Protoblastenia monticola*, 1935: 81 as *P. monticola*; Kušan 1953: 494 as *P. monticola*; Murati 1992: 313)
- Collema auriforme* (With.) Coppins & J.R. Laundon (Simić 1892: 453 as *C. granosum*, 1895: 139 as *C. granosum*; Katić 1903: 5 as *C. granosum* Wulf.; Murati 1993: 112)
- Collema crispum* (Huds.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Servit 1934: 130 as *C. cheileum*; Kušan 1953: 165 as *C. cheileum*; Gallé 1975: 291 as var. *crispum*; Murati 1993: 114; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Collema cristatum* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Simić 1892: 453 as *C. multifidum*, 1895: 139 as *C. multifidum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161 as *C. multifidum*; Servit 1934: 131 as '*C. multifidum* v. *jacobaeae-folium*'; Kušan 1953: 167 & 170 as *C. multifidum*; Murati 1993: 114; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Collema flaccidum* (Ach.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 453 as '*Synechoblastus flaccidus* α *major* Schaer.', 1895: 140 as *S. flaccidus*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 162 as *C. rupestre*; Servit 1934: 131 as *C. rupestre*; Kušan 1953: 163 as *C. rupestre*; Murati 1993: 115; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Collema fragrans* (Sm.) Ach. (Murati 1993: 115)
- Collema fuscovirens* (With.) J.R. Laundon (Servit 1934: 130 as *C. furvum*; Kušan 1953: 167 as *C. furvum*; Tatić & Veljović 1982: 70 as *C. furvum*; Murati 1993: 116; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Collema limosum* (Ach.) Ach. (Servit 1934: 130 as *C. glaucescens*; Kušan 1953: 167 as *C. glaucescens*; Murati 1993: 117)
- Collema multipartitum* Sm. (Murati 1993: 118)
- Collema nigrescens* (Huds.) DC. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161; Kušan 1953: 162; Murati 1992: 118)
- Collema polycarpon* Hoffm. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161; Servit 1934: 131 as '*P. polycarpum*'; Kušan 1953: 159 as '*P. polycarpum*'; Murati 1992: 119)
- Collema tenax* (Sw.) Ach. emend. Degel. (Simić 1892: 453 as '*C. pulposum* α *granulosum* Sw.', 1895: 139 as *C. pulposum*; Katić 1903: 5 as *C. pulposum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 162 as *C. pulposum*; Servit 1934: 131 as *C. pulposum*; Kušan 1953: 171 as *C. pulposum*; Gallé 1975: 291 as var. *tenax*; Murati 1993: 120)
- Collema undulatum* Laurer ex Flot. (Gallé 1974: 38; Murati 1993: 120)
- Cornicularia normoerica* (Gunnerus) Du Rietz (Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Dermatocarpon miniatum* (L.) W. Mann (Pančić 1859: 146 as *Endocarpon miniatum*; Simić 1892: 451 as '*E. miniatum* α *vulgaris*', 1895: 135 as *E. miniatum*, 1896: 9 as *E. miniatum*, 1897: 7 as *E. miniatum*, 1898: 15 as *E. miniatum*; Katić 1903: 5 as *E. miniatum*, 1907: 13 as *E. miniatum*, 1910: 39; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 160; Servit 1934: 124, 1935: 74; Kušan 1953: 73; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 328; Murati 1993: 184 as *D. intestiniforme*, 185; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Dibaeis baeomyces* (L. f.) Rambold & Hertel (Simić 1892: 453 as *Baeomyces roseus*, 1895: 129 as *B. roseus*; Murati 1992: 124 as *B. roseus*)
- Dimelaena oreina* (Ach.) Norman (Murati 1993: 220)
- Dimerella pineti* (Ach.) Vězda (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Diplochromis actinostomus* (Ach.) Zahlbr. (Simić 1892: 453 as *Limboria actinostoma*; Murati 1992: 187)
- Diplochromis muscorum* (Scop.) R. Sant. (Simić 1897: 7 as '*Urceolaria scruposa* (L.) β. *bryophylla* Ach.>'; Servit 1934: 127 as *D. bryophilus*; Kušan 1953: 137 as *D. bryophilus*; Murati 1992: 189)
- Diplochromis ocellatus* (Vill.) Norman (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Urceolaria ocellata* Vill.>'; Murati 1992: 189)
- Diplochromis scruposus* (Schreb.) Norman (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Urceolaria scruposa* L. α *vulgaris*', 1895: 126 & 147 as *U. scruposa*, 1900: 47 as *U. scruposa*; Katić 1907: 14 as '*U. scruposa* Ach. var. *vulgaris* Kbr.', 1910: 39 as '*U. scruposa* Ach. v. *vulgaris*'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161; Kušan 1953: 138; Gallé 1975: 291; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 190)
- Diplotomma alboatrum* (Hoffm.) Flot. (Simić 1892: 452 as *D. alboatrum* var. *epipolium*, 1895: 130, 1897: 7 as *D. alboatrum* var. *epipolium*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177 as *Buellia alboatra*; Servit 1935: 85 as *B. alboatra* var. *ambigua*; Kušan 1953: 551 as *B. alboatra*, 553 as *Buellia epipolia* var. *ambigua*; Murati 1992: 134 as *B. alboatra*, 135 as *Buellia ambigua*, 136 as *B. epipolia*; Kojić 2002: 144 as *B. alboatra*)
- Diplotomma venustum* Körb. (Servit 1935: 85 as *Buellia epipolia* var. *venusta*; Kušan 1953: 553)
- Elixia flexella* (Ach.) Lumbsch (Murati 1990: 50 as *Lithographa flexella*)
- Endocarpon adscendens* (Anzi) Müll. Arg. (Servit 1934: 124; Kušan 1953: 77 as *E. pallidum*; Gallé 1975: 290 as *E. pallidum*; Murati 1992: 192; Savić *et al.* 2006: 101)
- Endocarpon pusillum* Hedw. (Gallé 1974: 38, 1975: 290; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Evernia divaricata* (L.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174 as *Letharia divaricata*; Kušan 1953: 468; Murati 1992: 196; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Evernia prunastri* (L.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 451 as '*α vulgaris*', 1895: 115 & 145, 1896: 9, 1900: 47; Katić 1907: 13; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 173-174; Gallé 1935: 269, 1975: 293; Servit 1934: 147, 1935: 81; Rudski 1949: 65; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 470-471; Gajić 1988: 68, 1989: 97; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Murati 1992: 196; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178;

- Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 59; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Farnoldia hypocrita* (A. Massal.) Fröberg (Servít 1935: 76 as *Lecidea lithospersa*; Kušan 1953: 227 as *L. lithospersa*; Murati 1992: 230 as *Lecidea hypocrita*)
Farnoldia jurana (Schaer.) Hertel (Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Flavocetraria cucullata* (Bellardi) Kärnefelt & Thell (Murati 1992: 155 as *Cetraria cucullata*)
Flavocetraria nivalis (L.) Kärnefelt & Thell (Murati 1992: 157 as *Cetraria nivalis*; Dimović 2003: 144; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Flavoparmelia caperata* (L.) Hale (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Imbricaria caperata* Dill.', 1895: 120 as *Parmelia caperata*, 1898: 15 as *P. caperata*, 1900: 47 as *P. caperata*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 173 as *Parmelia cylisphora*; Servít 1934: 145 as *P. caperata*; Rudski 1949: 61 as *P. caperata*; Soška 1949: 110 as '*P. cylisphora*'; Kušan 1953: 459-460 as *P. caperata*; Gallé 1975: 293 as *P. caperata*; Gajić 1988: 68 as *P. caperata*, 1989: 96 as *P. caperata*; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66 as *P. caperata*; Murati 1993: 176; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. caperata*; Randelović 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 43; Savić 1996: 58, 1998: 339; Szabados 1998: 60 as *P. caperata*; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 110 as *P. caperata*, 2003: 145 as *P. caperata*)
- Fulgensia pruinosa* (Körb.) Poelt (Servít 1935: 85 as *Caloplaca pruinosa*; Kušan 1953: 521 as *C. pruinosa*)
Fulgensia schistidii (Anzi) Poelt (Servít 1935: 85 as *Caloplaca schistidii*; Kušan 1953: 524 as *C. schistidii*; Murati 1992: 199)
- Fuscidea cyathoides* (Ach.) V. Wirth & Vězda (Simić 1892: 452 as *Biatora rivulosa*, 1895: 129 as *B. rivulosa*; Murati 1992: 228; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Fuscopannaria saubinetii* (Mont.) P.M. Jørg. (Servít 1934: 132 as *Parmeliella saubinetii*; Kušan 1953: 191 as *Parmeliella saubinetii*; Murati 1992: 262 as *Pannaria saubinetii*)
- Graphis elegans* (Borrer ex Sm.) Ach. (Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
Graphis scripta (L.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 453 as '*α vulgaris*', 1895: 133 & 147, 1900: 47; Servít 1934: 127; Soška 1949: 109 as '*Graphidia scripta*'; Kušan 1953: 127; Murati 1993: 123; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 145)
- Gyalecta jenensis* (Batsch) Zahlbr. (Servít 1935: 75; Kušan 1953: 146; Murati 1992: 202; Stamenković 1998: 72)
Gyalecta truncigena (Ach.) Hepp (Servít 1934: 128, 1935: 75; Kušan 1953: 147; Murati 1992: 203)
- Heterodermia speciosa* (Wulfen) Trevis. (Dimović 2003: 145)
- Hymenelia epulotica* (Ach.) Lutzoni (Servít 1935: 75 as '*Jonaspis epulotica*'; Kušan 1953: 142 as '*Jonaspis epulotica*'; Murati 1992: 214 as *Jonaspis epulotica*)
Hymenelia heteromorpha (Kremp.) Lutzoni (Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
Hymenelia melanocarpa (Kremp.) Lutzoni (Servít 1934: 127 as '*Jonaspis cyrtaspis*'; Kušan 1953: 142 as '*Jonaspis cyrtaspis*'; Murati 1992: 214 as *Jonaspis melanocarpa*)
Hymenelia prevostii (Duby) Kremp. (Servít 1935: 79 as *Lecanora prevostii*; Kušan 1953: 366-367 as *L. prevostii*; Murati 1992: 109 & 208)
- Hyperphyscia adglutinata* (Flörke) H. Mayrhofer & Poelt (Servít 1934: 158 as *Physcia adglutinata*; Kušan 1953: 564 as *Physcia adglutinata*; Murati 1990: 50 as *Physciopsis adglutinata*, 1992: 299; Szabados 1998: 60 as *Physciopsis adglutinata*)
- Hypocenomys scalaris* (Ach.) M. Choisy (Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Hypogymnia farinacea* Zopf (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Hypogymnia physodes* (L.) Nyl. (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Imbricaria physoides* L. *α vulgaris*', 1895: 119 as '*Parmelia physoides*'; Katić 1907: 13 as *Parmelia physodes*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 171 as *P. physodes*; Gallé 1935: 267, 1975: 293; Kušan 1953: 428-429 as *P. physodes*; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185 as *P. physodes*; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111 as '*Parmelia physoides*'; Gajić 1988: 68 as *P. physodes*, 1989: 96 as *P. physodes*; Murati 1992: 211; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 43; Savić 1996: 58, 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 59; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 109, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Hypogymnia tubulosa* (Schaer.) Hav. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 171 as *Parmelia tubulosa*; Kušan 1953: 430 as *P. tubulosa*; Gallé 1975: 293; Gajić 1988: 68 as *P. tubulosa*; Murati 1992: 211; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Savić 1996: 58, 1998: 339; Szabados 1998: 59; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Hypogymnia vittata* (Ach.) Parrique (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 171 as *Parmelia vittata*; Kušan 1953: 430 as *P. vittata*; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 212)
- Icmadophila ericetorum* (L.) Zahlbr. (Simić 1892: 452 as *I. aeruginosa*, 1895: 124 as *I. aeruginosa*; Murati 1992: 213; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Imshaugia aleurites* (Ach.) S.L.F. Meyer (Simić 1892: 451 as *Imbricaria aleurites*, 1895: 119 as *I. aleurites*; Kušan 1953: 427 as *Parmeliopsis pallescens*; Murati 1992: 265; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *Parmeliopsis aleurites*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)

- Julella fallaciosa* (Stitzenb. ex Arnold) R.C. Harris (Gallé 1935: 265 as '*Polyblastiopsis fallaciosa* Stegh.', 1975: 291 as *P. fallaciosa*)
- Lasallia pustulata* (L.) Mérat (Katić 1903: 5 as *Umbilicaria pustulata*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *U. pustulata*; Kušan 1953: 319 as *U. pustulata*; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 214; Savić 1996: 58; Dimović 2001: 109; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanactis abietina* (Ach.) Körb. (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Lecania cyrtella* (Ach.) Th. Fr. (Servít 1934: 144; Kušan 1953: 415; Gallé 1975: 292; Murati 1992: 220; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecania dubitans* (Nyl.) A.L. Sm. (Servít 1934: 144 as *L. dimera*; Gallé 1935: 267 as *L. dimera*, 1975: 292 as *L. dimera*; Kušan 1953: 415 as *L. dimera*; Murati 1992: 220; Savić 1998: 337)
- Lecania erysibe* (Ach.) Mudd (Servít 1934: 144; Gallé 1935: 267, 1966: 29, 1975: 292; Kušan 1953: 416; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Lecania fuscella* (Schaer.) A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 144 as *L. syringea*; Kušan 1953: 418 as *L. syringea*; Murati 1992: 221)
- Lecania hyalina* (Fr.) R. Sant. (Servít 1934: 138 as *Catillaria globulosa*; Kušan 1953: 238 as *Lecidea minuta*; Murati 1992: 150 as *C. globulosa*)
- Lecania inundata* (Körb.) M. Mayrhofer (M. Mayrhofer 1988: 70; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecania naegelii* (Hepp) Diederich & van den Boom (Servít 1934: 139 as *Bacidia naegelii*; Kušan 1953: 260 as *B. naegelii*; Murati 1992: 119 as *B. naegelii*)
- Lecania nylanderiana* A. Massal. (Katić 1907: 14; Kušan 1953: 417; Murati 1992: 222)
- Lecania rabenhorstii* (Hepp) Arnold (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170 as *L. erysibe* var. *rabenhorstii*; Servít 1934: 144 as *L. erysibe* var. *rabenhorstii*; Servít 1935: 80 as *L. erysibe* var. *rabenhorstii*; Kušan 1953: 416 as *L. erysibe* var. *rabenhorstii*, 417)
- Lecanographa grumulosa* (Dufour) Egea & Torrente (Servít 1934: 126 as *Opegrapha grumulosa*; Kušan 1953: 121 as *O. grumulosa*)
- Lecanora agardhiana* Ach. (Servít 1935: 77; Kušan 1953: 370; Murati 1993: 132)
- Lecanora albella* (Pers.) Ach. (Simić 1900: 47 as *L. pallida*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169 as *L. pallida*; Gallé 1935: 266, 1975: 292 as *L. pallida*; Kušan 1953: 387 as *L. pallida*; Murati 1993: 143 as *L. pallida*)
- Lecanora albescens* (Hoffm.) Branth & Rostr. (Katić 1907: 13 as '*L. crenulata* f. *Somerfeltiana* Kbr.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169 as *L. galactina*; Gallé 1935: 266 as *L. galactina*, 1966: 29, 1974: 38, 1975: 292; Kušan 1953: 371; Murati 1993: 132; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Lecanora allophana* (Ach.) Nyl. (Katić 1903: 5 as *L. subfusca* var. *allophana*, 1907: 13 as *L. subfusca* var. *allophana* and as var. *margaritacea*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Servít 1934: 141, 1935: 77; Gallé 1935: 266, 1975: 292; Kušan 1953: 372; Murati 1993: 133; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72)
- Lecanora argentata* (Ach.) Malme (Servít 1935: 79 as *L. subfuscata*; Kušan 1953: 394 as *L. subfuscata*; Gallé 1975: 292 as *L. subfuscata*; Murati 1990: 49 as *L. subfuscata*, 1993: 133; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Lecanora campestris* (Schaer.) Hue (Gallé 1975: 292; Murati 1990: 49; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Lecanora carpinea* (L.) Vain. (Simić 1892: 452 as *L. pallida* var. *angulosa*, 1895: 125 as *L. pallida* var. *angulosa*; Katić 1910: 38 as *L. pallida* var. *angulosa*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Servít 1934: 141, 1935: 78; Gallé 1935: 266, 1975: 292; Soška 1949: 110; Kušan 1953: 376; Murati 1993: 134; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 339; Szabados 1998: 59; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Lecanora cenisia* Ach. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora chlarotera* Nyl. (Servít 1935: 78 as *L. crassula*; Kušan 1953: 378 & 380 as *L. crassula*; Murati 1993: 135; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora circumborealis* Brodo & Vitik. (Murati 1993: 136)
- Lecanora conizaeoides* Nyl. ex Cromb. (Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Savić 1998: 337; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Lecanora crenulata* Hook. (Servít 1935: 78; Kušan 1953: 380; Gallé 1974: 38, 1975: 292; Murati 1993: 137; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora dispersa* (Pers.) Sommerf. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Gallé 1935: 266, 1966: 29, 1974: 38, 1975: 292; Servít 1935: 78; Kušan 1936: 190, 1953: 381-382; Murati 1993: 138; Seaward & John 2005)
- Lecanora epibryon* (Ach.) Ach. (Murati 1993: 138)
- Lecanora expallens* Ach. (Murati 1993: 139)
- Lecanora flotoviana* Spreng. (Simić 1892: 452; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora glabrata* (Ach.) Malme (Randelović 1995: 20; Stamenković 1998: 72)
- Lecanora hagenii* (Ach.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 125; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Servít 1934: 142; Gallé 1935: 266, 1975: 292; Kušan 1953: 384; Murati 1993: 140; Savić 1998: 337; Seaward & John 2005: 67)
- Lecanora intricata* (Ach.) Ach. (Katić 1907: 13 as '*Lecanora polytropa* Th. Fr. var. *intricata* Schrad.>'; Kušan 1953: 384; Murati 1993: 141)
- Lecanora intumescens* (Rebent.) Rabenh. (Katić 1903: 5, 1907: 14; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Servít 1935: 79; Kušan 1953: 385; Murati 1990: 49, 1993: 141; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Todorović 1998: 75)

- Lecanora lojkaeana* Szatala (Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora orosthea* (Ach.) Ach. (Servít 1935: 79; Kušan 1953: 387)
- Lecanora polytropa* (Ehrh. ex Hoffm.) Rabenh. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Servít 1935: 79; Kušan 1936: 190, 1953: 389; Murati 1993: 143; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Lecanora pruinosa* Chaub. (Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20)
- Lecanora pulicaris* (Pers.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169 as *L. chlarona*; Servít 1934: 141 as *L. chlarona*, 1935: 78 as *L. chlarona*; Kušan 1936: 190 as *L. chlarona*, 1953: 377-379 as *L. chlarona*, *L. coilocarpa*; Murati 1993: 144; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *L. chlarona*; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72)
- Lecanora reuteri* Schaer. (Servít 1935: 79; Kušan 1953: 410; Murati 1993: 145)
- Lecanora rugosella* Zahlbr. (Gallé 1975: 292; Szabados 1998: 59)
- Lecanora rupicola* (L.) Zahlbr. (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Zeora sordida* Pers. var. *glaucoma* Ach.', 1895: 126 as *Z. sordida*; Katić 1910: 39 as '*Lecanora sordida* Th. Fr. var. *glaucoma*'; Kušan 1953: 390; Poelt 1975: 429 as '*Lecanora rupicola* coll.>'; Murati 1993: 145; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora saligna* (Schrad.) Zahlbr. (Murati 1990: 49, 1993: 145; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora sambuci* (Pers.) Nyl. (Servít 1934: 142; Kušan 1953: 391; Murati 1993: 146)
- Lecanora sarcopidoides* (A. Massal) A.L. Sm. (Murati 1990: 49)
- Lecanora subcarpineae* Szatala (Szabados 1998: 59; Dimović & Lököš 2003: 53)
- Lecanora subrugosa* Nyl. (Servít 1935: 79; Kušan 1953: 394; Gallé 1975: 292; Murati 1993: 147)
- Lecanora symmicta* (Ach.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Kušan 1953: 394; Gallé 1975: 292; Murati 1993: 148; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecanora umbrina* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Servít 1934: 142, 1935: 80; Gallé 1935: 267, 1974: 38, 1975: 292; Kušan 1953: 395; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Murati 1990: 49, 1993: 148)
- Lecanora varia* (Hoffm.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 452 as '*L. varia* Ehrh. *α. vulgaris*', 1895: 125; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 169; Kušan 1953: 396; Murati 1990: 49, 1993: 148; Savić 1998: 339; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecidea confluens* (Weber) Ach. (Katić 1907: 14 as '*L. confluens* Fr.>'; Kušan 1953: 219; Murati 1992: 228; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecidea confluentula* Müll. Arg. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecidea fuscoatra* (L.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165 as *L. fumosa*; Kušan 1953: 224; Murati 1992: 230; Kojić 2002: 143; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecidea lapicida* (Ach.) Ach. (Katić 1907: 14 as '*Lecidella lapicida* Arn.', 1910: 39 as *Lecidella pantherina*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165; Kušan 1953: 221 as *Lecidea declinans*)
- Lecidea plana* (J. Lahm) Nyl. (Katić 1910: 39 as *Lecidea latypea*; Kušan 1953: 226 as *L. latypaea*; Murati 1992: 233)
- Lecidea sudetica* Körb. (Katić 1907: 14 as *Lecidella sudetica* (Körb.) Stein; Kušan 1953: 233)
- Lecidea tessellata* Flörke (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164; Kušan 1953: 220 as *L. cyanea*; Poelt 1975: 429; Murati 1992: 235; Savić *et al.* 2006: 102)
- Lecidella carpathica* Körb. (Krause & Klement 1958: 7 as *Lecidea latypiza*; Poelt 1975: 429; Leuckert *et al.* 1990: 268; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 239; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Lecidella elaeochroma* (Ach.) M. Choisy (Simić 1892: 452 as *Lecidea enteroleuca*, 1895: 131 & 147 as *L. enteroleuca*, 1900: 47 as *Lecidea parasema*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164 as *L. parasema* & 164 as *Lecidea olivacea*; Servít 1934: 132 as *Lecidea elaeochroma* & 133 as *L. parasema*, 1935: 76 as *L. elaeochroma*, *L. parasema*; Gallé 1935: 266 as *L. elaeochroma*, *L. parasema*, 1975: 291 as '*L. elaeochroma* f. *limitata* (Ach.) Vain.', *L. parasema*; Kušan 1936: 184 as *L. parasema*, 1953: 222-223 as *L. elaeochroma* & 230 as *L. parasema*; Soška 1949: 109 as *L. olivacea*, *L. parasema*; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 239; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145)
- Lecidella euphorea* (Flörke) Hertel (Servít 1934: 133 as *Lecidea glomerulosa*; Kušan 1953: 224 as *L. glomerulosa*; Gallé 1975: 291 as *L. glomerulosa*; Szabados 1998: 59; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Lecidella stigmattea* (Ach.) Hertel & Leuckert (Servít 1934: 133 as *Lecidea vulgata*, 1935: 76 as *L. vulgata*; Kušan 1953: 225 as '*L. incongrua* f. *spathea*'; Krause & Klement 1958: 7 as *Lecidea stigmattea*; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 240; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Lempholemma polyanthes* (Bernh.) Malme (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161 as *L. fasciculare*; Kušan 1953: 157 as *L. fasciculare*; Murati 1993: 152 as *L. myriococcum*)
- Lepraria elobata* Tønsberg (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Lepraria incana* (L.) Ach. (Murati 1993: 153; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 43; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 59; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145)
- Lepraria lobificans* Nyl. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Lepraria neglecta* (Nyl.) Lettau (Murati 1993: 153)
- Lepraria nivalis* J.R. Laundon (Murati 1993: 152 as '*Lepraria crassissima* (Hue) Lettau'.
Note: The P+ reaction in Murati's description would indicate that this is *L. nivalis*.)
- Lepraria membranacea* (Dicks.) Vain. (Murati 1993: 153 as *Leproloma membranacea*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Leprocaulon microscopicum* (Vill.) Gams (Murati 1990: 49, 1993: 153)
- Leptogium hildenbrandii* (Garov.) Nyl. (Servít 1934: 131)

- Leptogium lichenoides* (L.) Zahlbr. (Simić 1892: 453 as *L. lacerum*, 1895: 139 & 147 as *L. lacerum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 162; Servít 1934: 131, 1935: 75 as *L. pulvinatum*; Kušan 1953: 178; Gallé 1975: 291; Murati 1992: 245; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Leptogium saturninum* (Dicks.) Nyl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 162; Kušan 1953: 183; Murati 1990: 49, 1992: 246)
- Leptogium teretiusculum* (Wallr.) Arnold (Servít 1934: 131; Kušan 1953: 175; Murati 1992: 247)
- Letharia vulpina* (L.) Hue (Murati 1993: 154; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Lobaria amplissima* (Scop.) Forssell (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163; Kušan 1953: 196; Murati 1992: 249; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Lobaria linita* (Ach.) Rabenh. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163; Kušan 1953: 196; Murati 1992: 249; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Lobaria pulmonaria* (L.) Hoffm. (Simić 1892: 451 as *Sticta pulmonaria*, 1895: 118 as *S. pulmonaria*; Katić 1903: 4 as '*S. pulmonaria* Schaer.', 1907: 13 as '*S. pulmonaria* Schaer.'; Mišić *et al.* 1978: 177 & 201 as '*L. pulmonacea*'; Gajić 1988: 68, 1989: 96; Murati 1992: 249; Savić 1996: 58; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Lobaria scrobiculata* (Scop.) DC. (Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 250; Savić 1996: 59)
- Lobothallia praeradiosa* (Nyl.) Hafellner (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Lobothallia radiosa* (Hoffm.) Hafellner (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170 as *Lecanora subcircinata*; Servít 1934: 142 as *Lecanora radiosa*; Kušan 1953: 407 & 409 as *L. radiosa*; Krause & Klement 1958: 6 as *Placodium subcircinatum*; Poelt 1975: 429 as *Aspicilia radiosa*; Murati 1992: 109 as *A. radiosa*; Navarro-Rosinés & Hafellner 1996: 222; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Loxospora cismonica* (Beltram.) Hafellner (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Megalaria pulverea* (Borrer) Hafellner & E. Schreiner (Gallé 1975: 291 as *Catillaria pulverea*)
- Megaspora verrucosa* (Ach.) Hafellner & V. Wirth (Murati 1990: 48 as *Aspicilia verrucosa*)
- Melanelia elegantula* (Zahlbr.) Essl. (Szabados 1998: 60 as *Parmelia elegantula*)
- Melanelia exasperata* (De Not.) Essl. (Simić 1895: 120 & 146 as *Parmelia aspidota*, 1900: 47 as *P. aspidota*; Katić 1910: 38 as *Parmelia exasperata*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *P. aspidota*; Servít 1934: 145 as *P. aspidota*, 1935: 80 as *P. aspidota*; Kušan 1953: 435-436 as *P. aspidota*; Gallé 1975: 293 as *Parmelia aspera*; Murati 1990: 50 as *P. exasperata*; Murati 1993: 177; Stamenković 1998: 72)
- Melanelia exasperatula* (Nyl.) Essl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *Parmelia exasperatula*; Servít 1935: 80 as *P. exasperatula*; Kušan 1936: 193 as *P. exasperatula*, 1953: 437 as *P. exasperatula*; Gallé 1975: 293 as *P. exasperatula*; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. exasperatula*; Murati 1993: 178; Stamenković 1995: 43; Savić 1998: 339)
- Melanelia fuliginosa* (Fr. ex Duby) Essl. subsp. *fuliginosa* (Servít 1934: 145 as *Parmelia fuliginosa*; Gallé 1935: 268 as *P. fuliginosa*, 1975: 293 as *P. fuliginosa*; Soška 1949: 110 as '*Parmelia fuliginosa* f. *lutescens*'; Kušan 1953: 438 as *P. fuliginosa*; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. fuliginosa*; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. fuliginosa*; Stamenković 1995: 43, 1998: 72; Savić 1996: 59, 1998: 339; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Melanelia fuliginosa* subsp. *glabratula* (Lamy) Coppins (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *Parmelia fuliginosa* var. *laetevirens*; Servít 1934: 146 as *Parmelia laetevirens*, 1935: 80 as *P. laetevirens*; Kušan 1953: 439 as *Parmelia fuliginosa* var. *laetevirens*; Murati 1993: 178 as *M. glabratula*; Savić 1996: 59; Szabados 1998: 60 as *Parmelia glabratula*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Melanelia glabra* (Schaer.) Essl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *P. glabra*; Servít 1934: 145 as *Parmelia glabra*; Gallé 1935: 268 as *P. glabra*, 1975: 293 as *P. glabra*; Servít 1935: 80 as *P. glabra*; Kušan 1953: 440-441 as *P. glabra*; Murati 1993: 178; Stamenković 1995: 43)
- Melanelia olivacea* (L.) Essl. (Simić 1897: 7 as *Parmelia olivacea*, 1900: 47 as *P. olivacea*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *P. olivacea*; Rudski 1949: 61 as *P. olivacea*; Soška 1949: 110 as *P. olivacea*; Kušan 1953: 442 as *P. olivacea*; Gallé 1975: 293 as *P. olivacea*; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66 as *P. olivacea*; Murati 1993: 180)
- Melanelia soreliata* (Ach.) Goward & Ahti (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *Parmelia soreliata*; Kušan 1953: 444 as *Parmelia soreliata*; Murati 1993: 184 as *M. soreliosa*)
- Melanelia subargentifera* (Nyl.) Essl. (Servít 1934: 147 as *Parmelia verruculifera*, 1935: 81 as *P. verruculifera*; Kušan 1953: 445 as *P. verruculifera*; Gallé 1975: 293 as *Parmelia subargentifera*; Murati 1990: 50 as *P. subargentifera*, 1993: 185; Stamenković 1995: 43)
- Melanelia subaurifera* (Nyl.) Essl. (Servít 1934: 146 as *Parmelia subaurifera*; Kušan 1953: 445 as *P. subaurifera*; Murati 1993: 185; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Menegazzia terebrata* (Hoffm.) A. Massal. (Dimović 2003: 145)
- Micarea denigrata* (Fr.) Hedl. (Murati 1990: 50)
- Micarea melanaida* (Nyl.) Coppins (Gallé 1974: 37 as *Toninia zsakii*, 1975: 291 as *T. zsakii*)
- Micarea peliocarpa* (Anzi) Coppins & R. Sant. (Gallé 1975: 291 as '*Bacidia triseptata* (Naeg.) Zahlbr.')
- Micarea prasina* Fr. (Servít 1934: 138 as *Catillaria prasina*; Kušan 1953: 254 as *C. prasina*; Murati 1993: 160; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)

- Moelleropsis nebulosa* (Hoffm.) Gyeln. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163 as *Pannaria nebulosa*; Servít 1934: 132 as *P. nebulosa*; Kušan 1953: 193 as *P. nebulosa*; Murati 1992: 264)
- Mycobilimbia epixanthoides* (Nyl.) Hafellner & Türk (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Mycobilimbia lurida* (Ach.) Hafellner & Türk (Servít 1935: 76 as *Lecidea lurida*; Kušan 1953: 245 as *L. lurida*; Murati 1992: 232 as *L. lurida*, 317 as '*Psora lurida* (With.) DC.>'; Kojić 2002: 143 as *L. lurida*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Mycobilimbia pilularis* (Körb.) Hafellner & Türk (Anonymous 1975: 15 as *Bacidia sphaeroides*; Murati 1992: 121 as *Biatora pilularis*)
- Mycobilimbia tetramera* (De Not.) Vitik. *et al.* (Murati 1990: 48 as *Bacidia fusca*)
- Naetrocymbe fraxini* (A. Massal.) R.C. Harris (Servít 1934: 125 as *Arthopyrenia fraxini*; Kušan 1953: 81 as *A. fraxini*; Murati 1992: 95 as *A. fraxini*)
- Naetrocymbe punctiformis* (Pers.) R.C. Harris (Simić 1892: 453 as *Arthopyrenia analepta*, 1895 as *A. analepta*; Servít 1934: 125 as *Arthopyrenia punctiformis*, 1935: 74 as *A. punctiformis*; Kušan 1953: 79, 80 as *A. punctiformis*; Murati 1992: 97 as *A. punctiformis*)
- Naetrocymbe rhypona* (Ach.) R.C. Harris (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Naetrocymbe saxicola* (A. Massal.) R.C. Harris (Servít 1935: 75 as *Arthopyrenia saxicola*; Kušan 1953: 82 as *A. saxicola*; Murati 1992: 98 as *A. saxicola*)
- Neofuscelia loxodes* (Nyl.) Essl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *Parmelia isidiotyta*; Kušan 1953: 442 as *P. isidiotyta*; Murati 1993: 179)
- Neofuscelia pulla* (Ach.) Essl. (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Imbricaria olivacea* var. *prolixa* Ach.', 1895: 120 as '*Imbricaria olivacea* var. *prolixa* Ach.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *Parmelia prolixa*; Servít 1935: 80 as *P. prolixa*; Kušan 1953: 443 as *P. prolixa*; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 330 as *P. prolixa*; Murati 1990: 50 as *Parmelia pulla*, 1993: 182)
- Neofuscelia verruculifera* (Nyl.) Essl. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Nephroma bellum* (Spreng.) Tuck. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163 as *N. laevigatum*; Kušan 1953: 202 as *N. laevigatum*)
- Nephroma parile* (Ach.) Ach. (Katić 1904: 3 as '*Nephromium laevigatum*. var. *genuinum* Kbr. f. *soridiatum* Schaer.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163; Servít 1934: 132 as '*Nephromium parile* f. *hybridum*'; Kušan 1953: 203 as '*N. laevigatum* f. *parile*'; Murati 1992: 253)
- Nephroma resupinatum* (L.) Ach. (Katić 1907: 13 as *Nephromium tomentosum*, 1910: 40 as *N. tomentosum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163; Kušan 1953: 205; Murati 1992: 254; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Normandina pulchella* (Borrer) Nyl. (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Ochrolechia androgyna* (Hoffm.) Arnold (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Ochrolechia arborea* (Kreyer) Almb. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Ochrolechia parella* (L.) A. Massal. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170; Servít 1934: 144; Kušan 1953: 413; Murati 1992: 256; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Ochrolechia turneri* (Sm.) Hasselrot (Erichsen 1936: 677 as *Pertusaria henrici* var. *pallescens*; Hanko *et al.* 1985: 193)
- Opegrapha atra* Pers. (Simić 1892: 453 as '*α vulgaris* Kbr.', 1895: 134; Katić 1903: 5; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161; Servít 1934: 126; Soška 1949: 109; Kušan 1953: 122; Murati 1993: 166; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Opegrapha culmigena* Libert (Savić 1998: 337)
- Opegrapha rufescens* Pers. (Servít 1934: 126; Kušan 1953: 123 as *O. herpetica* var. *rufescens*; Murati 1993: 168)
- Opegrapha varia* Pers. (Simić 1892: 453, 1895: 134, 1900: 47; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161 as *O. lichenoides*; Servít 1935: 75 as *O. diaphora*; Kušan 1953: 124 as *O. lichenoides*; Murati 1993: 169; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Opegrapha viridis* (Ach.) Behlen & Desberger (Murati 1993: 169 as '*Opegrapha viridis* Pers.')
- Opegrapha vulgata* Ach. (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Ophioparma ventosa* (L.) Norman (Katić 1907: 13 as *Haematomma ventosum*; Kušan 1953: 420 as *H. ventosum*; Murati 1992: 205)
- Pachyphiale fagicola* (Hepp) Zwackh (Servít 1934: 128, 1935: 75; Kušan 1953: 148; Murati 1992: 258)
- Pannaria conoplea* (Ach.) Bory (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163 as *Pannaria lanuginosa sensu* Szatala; Kušan 1953: 194 as '*P. rubiginosa* v. *lanuginosa*'; Murati 1992: 260; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Pannaria rubiginosa* (Ach.) Bory (Murati 1992: 262; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Parmelia saxatilis* (L.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Imbricaria saxatilis α leucochroa* Wallr.', 1895: 119 & 146, 1898: 15, 1900: 47; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 173; Rudski 1949: 61; Soška 1949: 110; Kušan 1953: 453; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111; Gallé 1975: 293; Gajić 1983: 40; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Murati 1993: 183; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 44; Savić 1996: 59, 1998: 337; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145)
- Parmelia sulcata* Taylor (Katić 1907: 13 as '*P. saxatilis* var. *sulcata* Nyl.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 173; Servít 1934: 147, 1935: 81; Gallé 1935: 268, 1975: 293; Soška 1949: 110 as '*f. rubescens*'; Kušan 1953: 456-457; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Murati 1993: 186; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Randelović 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 60; Todorović 1998:

- 75; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Seaward & John 2005: 67)
- Parmelina pastillifera* (Harm.) Hale (Poelt 1975: 429 as *Parmelia pastillifera*; Murati 1990: 50 as *P. pastillifera*, 1993: 181; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72)
- Parmelina quercina* (Willd.) Hale (Servít 1934: 146 as *Parmelia quercina*, 1935: 80 as *P. quercina*; Kušan 1953: 451 as *P. quercina*; Gallé 1975: 293 as *P. quercina*; Murati 1993: 182; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. quercina*; Randelović 1995: 20 as *P. quercina*; Stamenković 1998: 72; Dimović 2003: 145 as *P. quercina*)
- Parmelina tiliacea* (Hoffm.) Hale (Simić 1895: 119 & 146 as *Parmelia tiliacea*, 1900: 47 as *P. tiliacea*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *P. tiliacea*, 173 as *Parmelia scortea*; Gallé 1935: 268 as *P. tiliacea*, 1975: 293 as *P. tiliacea*; Servít 1935: 82 as *P. scortea*; Soška 1949: 110 as *P. tiliacea*; Kušan 1953: 455 as *P. scortea*; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185 as *P. tiliacea*; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111 as *P. tiliacea*; Gajić 1983: 40 as *P. tiliacea*; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66 as *P. tiliacea*; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. scortea*; Murati 1993: 186; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. scortea*; Savić 1998: 337; Dimović 2001: 110 as *P. tiliacea*, 2003: 145 as *P. tiliacea*)
- Parmeliopsis ambigua* (Wulfen) Nyl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 171; Kušan 1953: 426; Murati 1990: 50; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145)
- Parmeliopsis hyperopta* (Ach.) Arnold (Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 265; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92)
- Parmotrema chinense* (Osbeck) Hale & Ahti (Katić 1903: 4 as '*Parmelia perlata* L.', 1907: 13 as *Parmelia perlata*; Servít 1934: 147 as *Parmelia trichotera*; Kušan 1953: 458 as *P. trichotera*, 461 as *P. perlata*; Murati 1993: 181 as *P. perlatum*)
- Peltigera apthosa* (L.) Willd. (Simić 1895: 146, 1897: 6, 1898: 15; Katić 1910: 40; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163; Kušan 1953: 207; Murati 1992: 267)
- Peltigera canina* (L.) Willd. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 117 & 146, 1896: 9, 1897: 7, 1898: 15, 1900: 47; Katić 1910: 40; Servít 1934: 132; Kušan 1936: 182, 1953: 208; Rudski 1949: 61; Soška 1949: 110; Gallé 1975: 291; Murati 1992: 268; Savić 1996: 59; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Peltigera collina* (Ach.) Schrad. (Murati 1990: 50)
- Peltigera didactyla* (With.) J.R. Laundon (Simić 1895: 146 as *P. spuria*, 1897: 7 as *P. spuria*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164 as *P. spuria*; Kušan 1953: 217 as *P. spuria*; Murati 1992: 268)
- Peltigera extenuata* (Nyl.) Vain. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Peltigera horizontalis* (Huds.) Baumg. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 118 & 146, 1896: 9, 1898: 15; Katić 1903: 4; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164; Servít 1934: 132; Soška 1949: 110; Kušan 1953: 210; Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 269; Vitikainen 1994: 46; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Peltigera leucophlebia* (Nyl.) Gyeln. (Vitikainen 1994: 55; Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Peltigera malacea* (Ach.) Funck (Dimović 2003: 145)
- Peltigera polydactyla* (Neck.) Hoffm. (Simić 1892: 451 as 'var. *vulgaris*', 1895: 117 & 146, 1896: 9, 1897: 7, 1898: 15; Katić 1903: 4; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164; Kušan 1953: 212; Murati 1992: 270; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 67-68; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Peltigera praetextata* (Flörke ex Sommerf.) Zopf (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164; Gyelnik 1927: 132; Servít 1934: 132; Kušan 1953: 213; Murati 1992: 271)
- Peltigera rufescens* (Weiss) Humb. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 117; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163 as *P. canina* f. *ulorrhiza*, 164; Kušan 1953: 209 & 215, Servít 1934: 132, 1935: 76 as '*P. canina* v. *incusa*'; Murati 1992: 272; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 67; Kojić 2002: 143; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Peltigera venosa* (L.) Hoffm. (Simić 1895: 146, 1897: 7, 1898: 15; Servít 1935: 76; Kušan 1953: 207; Murati 1992: 273; Vitikainen 1994: 86; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 68)
- Peltula euploca* (Ach.) Poelt (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 162 as *Heppia guepinii*; Kušan 1953: 184 as *H. guepinii*; Murati 1993: 190)
- Pertusaria albescens* (Huds.) M. Choisy & Werner (Simić 1892: 453 as '*P. communis* α *variolosa* Wallr.', 1895: 138 as *P. communis* var. *variolosa*, 1900: 47 as '*P. communis* var. *variolosa*'; Erichsen 1936: 664 as *P. discoidea*, 671 as *P. henrici*; Kušan 1953: 352-353; Gallé 1975: 292 as *P. globulifera*; Murati 1992: 276; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Pertusaria amara* (Ach.) Nyl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as *P. faginea*; Servít 1935: 77; Erichsen 1940: 36 as *P. amara* var. *concentrica*; Soška 1949: 110 as *P. faginea*; Kušan 1953: 346-347; Murati 1992: 276; Savić 1998: 339; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145)
- Pertusaria aspergilla* (Ach.) J.R. Laundon (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Pertusaria chiodectonoides* Bagl. ex A. Massal. (Murati 1992: 277)
- Pertusaria coccodes* (Ach.) Nyl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168; Kušan 1953: 334; Murati 1992: 277; Savić 1998: 337)
- Pertusaria corallina* (L.) Arnold (Katić 1907: 14; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168; Kušan 1953: 347; Murati 1992: 278)
- Pertusaria coronata* (Ach.) Th. Fr. (Katić 1907: 14; Kušan 1953: 334; Murati 1992: 278)
- Pertusaria flavida* (DC.) J.R. Laundon (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Pertusaria hemisphaerica* (Flörke) Erichsen (Murati 1990: 50; Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Pertusaria lactea* (L.) Arnold (Pančić 1859: 146 as '*Variolaria lactea* Ach.'; Katić 1910: 39 as '*P. lactea* Nyl.'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168; Kušan 1953: 344; Murati 1992: 280)

- Pertusaria leioplaca* DC. (Katić 1904: 4 as *P. leucostoma*; Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53; Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Pertusaria multipuncta* (Turner) Nyl. (Gallé 1975: 292 as '*P. leptospora* var. *ommittens* Erichs.')
- Pertusaria pertusa* (Weigel) Tuck. (Simić 1895: 138 as *P. communis*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168 as *P. communis*; Gallé 1935: 266 as *P. pertusa* var. *rupestris*, 1975: 292; Servít 1935: 77; Kušan 1953: 336; Murati 1992: 280)
- Pertusaria schaeereri* Hafellner (Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. isidioides*; Todorović 1998: 75 as *P. isidioides*)
- Pertusaria trachythallina* Erichsen (Erichsen 1936 as *P. laevigata*; Kušan 1953: 348 as *P. laevigata*; Murati 1992: 283)
- Petractis clausa* (Hoffm.) Kremp. (Servít 1935: 75; Kušan 1953: 141; Murati 1993: 191)
- Petractis hypoleuca* (Ach.) Vězda (Savić *et al.* 2006: 103)
- Phaeophyscia cernoborskyi* (Nádv.) Essl. (Murati 1990: 50 as *Physcia cernoborskyi*)
- Phaeophyscia chloantha* (Ach.) Moberg (Gallé 1975: 295 as *Physcia luganensis*; Szabados 1998: 60 as *P. luganensis*)
- Phaeophyscia ciliata* (Hoffm.) Moberg (Servít 1934: 159 as *Physcia ciliata*; Kušan 1953: 575 as *Physcia obscura* var. *ciliata*; Murati 1992: 287)
- Phaeophyscia endococcina* (Körb.) Moberg (Dimović 2001: 110)
- Phaeophyscia nigricans* (Flörke) Moberg (Gallé 1935: 271 as *Physcia sciastrella*, 1975: 295 as *Physcia nigricans*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Phaeophyscia orbicularis* (Neck.) Moberg (Simić 1892: 451 as *Physcia obscura* α *orbicularis*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 179; Servít 1934: 159 as *P. obscura* f. *orbicularis*, 160 as *Physcia virella*; Gallé 1935: 271 as *P. virella*, 1966: 30 as *Physcia orbicularis*, 1975: 295 as *P. orbicularis*; Kušan 1953: 574 as *P. obscura* f. *orbicularis*, 582 as *P. virella*; Murati 1990: 50 as *P. orbicularis*, 1992: 289; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. orbicularis*; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. orbicularis*; Randelović 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 60; Todorović 1998: 75; Kojić 2002: 144; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Phaeophyscia sciastra* (Ach.) Moberg (Gallé 1975: 295 as *Physcia sciastra*)
- Phaeorrhiza nimbosea* (Fr.) H. Mayrhofer & Poelt (Murati 1990: 50)
- Pblyctis agelaea* (Ach.) Flot. (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 126; Kušan 1953: 421; Gallé 1975: 292; Murati 1992: 291)
- Pblyctis argena* (Spreng.) Flot. (Gallé 1935: 267, 1975: 292; Servít 1935: 80; Kušan 1953: 421; Murati 1992: 291; Szabados 1998: 60; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Physcia adscendens* (Th. Fr.) H. Olivier (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Physcia stellaris* α *ascendens*'; Servít 1934: 158; Gallé 1935: 270-271 as *Physcia hispida*, 1975: 295; Servít 1935: 86; Kušan 1953: 565; Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 293; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Randelović 1995: 20; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 60; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Seaward & John 2005: 67)
- Physcia aipolia* (Humb.) Hampe (Katić 1910: 38; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178; Servít 1934: 158, 1935: 86; Gallé 1935: 270, 1975: 295; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 566-567; Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 293; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72; Savić 1996: 60, 1998: 339; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Physcia biziana* (A. Massal.) Zahlbr. (Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Physcia caesia* (Hoffm.) Fűrnr. (Simić 1897: 7; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 568; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Gallé 1975: 295 and as *Physcia wainioi*; Gajić 1983: 40; Murati 1990: 50 as *P. wainioi*, 1992: 294; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Savić 1998: 337; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Physcia dimidiata* (Arnold) Nyl. (Murati 1992: 295; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Physcia dubia* (Hoffm.) Lettau (Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Gallé 1975: 295; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Savić 1998: 339)
- Physcia leptalea* (Ach.) DC. (Gallé 1975: 295; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178)
- Physcia stellaris* (L.) Nyl. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 121; Katić 1903: 4; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178; Servít 1934: 159, 1935: 86; Gallé 1935: 271, 1975: 295; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 579-580; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 112; Gajić 1983: 40; Murati 1992: 296; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Randelović 1995: 20; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 44; Savić 1998: 337; Stamenković 1998: 72; Dimović 2001: 110, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Physcia tenella* (Scop.) DC. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178; Servít 1934: 159 as *Physcia hispida*; Kušan 1953: 571 as *P. hispida*; Gallé 1974: 39, 1975: 295; Murati 1992: 296; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72; Savić 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 60; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 144; Seaward & John 2005: 67)
- Physcia tribacia* (Ach.) Nyl. (Gallé 1935: 271, 1975: 295)
- Physconia detersa* (Nyl.) Poelt (Servít 1934: 159 as *Physcia grisea* var. *detersa*, 1935: 86; Kušan 1953: 569 as *P. grisea* var. *detersa*; Murati 1992: 299)
- Physconia distorta* (With.) J.R. Laundon (Simić 1895: 121 as '*Physcia pulverulenta* f. *angustata* Schaer.', 1897: 7 as *P. pulverulenta*; Katić 1907: 13 as *Physcia pulverulenta* Nyl.; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178 as *P. pulverulenta*; Servít 1934: 159 as *P. pulverulenta*, 1935: 86 as *P. pulverulenta* var. *angustata*; Soška 1949: 111 as *P. pulverulenta* f. *turgida* Schaer.; Kušan 1953: 576-578 as *P. pulverulenta*;

- Marinović & Bata 1967: 185 as *P. pulverulenta*; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 112 as *P. pulverulenta*; Gallé 1975: 296 as *P. pulverulenta*; Murati 1992: 299; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. pulverulenta*; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. pulverulenta*; Stamenković 1995: 44; Savić 1998: 339; Todorović 1998: 75; Kojić 2002: 144)
- Physconia enteroxantha* (Nyl.) Poelt (Servít 1934: 159 as '*Physcia grisea* var. *enteroxanthella*', 1935: 86 as '*P. grisea* var. *enteroxanthella*'; Kušan 1953: 573 as '*Physcia leucoleiptes* f. *enteroxanthella*'; Murati 1992: 300)
- Physconia grisea* (Lam.) Poelt (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178 as *Physcia grisea*; Servít 1934: 159 as *P. grisea* var. *pityrea*; Gallé 1935: 271 as *P. grises*, 1975: 295; Kušan 1953: 569 as *P. grisea*; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 330 as *P. grisea*; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. grisea*; Murati 1992: 300; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. grisea*; Savić 1998: 337; Stamenković 1998: 72; Szabados 1998: 60; Todorović 1998: 75)
- Physconia perisidiosa* (Erichsen) Moberg (Gallé 1975: 295 as *Physcia farrea*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Physconia venusta* (Ach.) Poelt (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 178 as *Physcia venusta*; Servít 1934: 159 as *Physcia pulverulenta* var. *venusta*; Kušan 1953: 581 as *P. venusta*; Murati 1992: 301; Stamenković 1995: 44)
- Piccolia ochrophora* (Nyl.) Hafellner (Servít 1934: 140 as *Biatorella ochrophora*; Magnusson 1935-1936: 31 as *B. ochrophora*; Kušan 1953: 322 as *B. ochrophora*; Murati 1992: 126 as *B. ochrophora*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Placidium lachneum* (Ach.) de Lesd. (Servít 1934: 123 as *Dermatocarpon lachneum*; Kušan 1953: 69 as *D. lachneum*; Murati 1992: 146 as *D. lachneum*)
- Placidium pilosellum* (Breuss) Breuss (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Placidium rufescens* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 160 as *Dermatocarpon rufescens*; Servít 1935: 74 as *D. rufescens*; Kušan 1953: 68 as *D. rufescens*; Breuss 1990: 111 as *C. rufescens*; Murati 1992: 146 as *Catapyrenium rufescens*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Placidium squamulosum* (Ach.) Breuss (Gallé 1974: 38 as *Dermatocarpon hepaticum*; Murati 1992: 146 as *Catapyrenium squamulosum*)
- Placocarpus schaeferi* (Fr.) Breuss (Servít 1935: 74 as *Dermatocarpon monstrosum*; Kušan 1953: 71 as *D. monstrosum*; Murati 1993: 274; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Placopyrenium tatrense* (Vězda) Breuss (Murati 1993: 274 as *Placidiopsis tatrensis*)
- Placopyrenium trachyticum* (Hazsl.) Breuss (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 160 as *Dermatocarpon trachyticum*; Servít 1934: 124 as *D. trachyticum*; Kušan 1953: 70 as *D. trachyticum*)
- Placynthiella icmalea* (Ach.) Coppins & P. James (Seaward & John 2005: 67; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Placynthiella oligotropha* (Schrad.) Coppins & P. James (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Placyntbiella uliginosa* (Schrad.) Coppins & P. James (Simić 1892: 452 as *Biatora uliginosa*, 1895: 129 as '*B. uliginosa* (Schrad.)'; Murati 1992: 235)
- Placyntbium nigrum* (Huds.) Gray (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 162; Servít 1934: 132, 1935: 75; Kušan 1953: 186; Tatić & Veljović 1982: 70 as '*P. nigricans*'; Murati 1992: 304; Kojić 2002: 144; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Platismatia glauca* (L.) W.L. Culb. & C.F. Culb. (Simić 1892: 451 as *Cetraria glauca*, 1895: 116 as *C. glauca*; Kušan 1953: 463 as *C. glauca*; Murati 1992: 159; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Pleurosticta acetabulum* (Neck.) Elix & Lumbsch (Simić 1895: 120 & 146 as *Parmelia acetabulum*; Gallé 1935: 268 as *P. acetabulum*, 1975: 293 as *P. acetabulum*; Murati 1993: 175 as *Melanelia acetabulum*; Szabados 1998: 60 as *P. acetabulum*; Dimović 2001: 111 as *P. acetabulum*, 2003: 145 as *P. acetabulum*)
- Polyblastia deminuta* Arnold (Servít 1935: 74; Kušan 1953: 59; Murati 1993: 197)
- Polyblastia dermatodes* A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 123; Kušan 1953: 60; Murati 1993: 197)
- Polyblastia fuscoargillacea* Anzi (Servít 1935: 74 as *P. abstrahenda*; Kušan 1953: 61 as *P. abstrahenda*; Murati 1993: 197)
- Polyblastia philaea* Zschacke (Gallé 1975: 290)
- Polysporina lapponica* (Ach. ex Schaer.) Degel. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Polysporina simplex* (Davies) Vězda (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *Biatorella simplex*; Kušan 1953: 323 as *Sarcogyne simplex*; Murati 1992: 306; Kojić 2002: 144; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Porpidia cinereoatra* (Ach.) Hertel & Knoph (Servít 1934: 133 as *Lecidea meiospora*)
- Porpidia crustulata* (Ach.) Hertel & Knoph (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Lecidea crustulata* Flk. α *vulgaris*', 1895: 130 as *L. crustulata*; Murati 1992: 309; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Porpidia macrocarpa* (DC.) Hertel & A.J. Schwab (Simić 1897: 7 as *Lecidea macrocarpa*; Katić 1907: 14 as *Lecidea platycarpa*, 1910: 39 as '*L. macrocarpa* Ach.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165 as *L. contigua*; Kušan 1953: 228 as *L. macrocarpa*; Murati 1992: 309)
- Porpidia musiva* (Körb.) Hertel & Knoph (Katić 1907: 14 as *Lecidea musiva*; Murati 1992: 309)
- Porpidia soredizodes* (Lam. ex Nyl.) J.R. Laundon (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Porpidia tuberculosa* (Sm.) Hertel & Knoph (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Protoblastenia calva* (Dicks.) Zahlbr. (Servít 1935: 81; Kušan 1953: 489; Murati 1992: 311)

- Protoblastenia incrustans* (DC.) J. Steiner (Servít 1935: 81; Kušan 1953: 493; Murati 1992: 312)
- Protoblastenia rupestris* (Scop.) J. Steiner (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175; Servít 1934: 148, 1935: 81; Kušan 1953: 495; Murati 1992: 313; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Protopannaria pezizoides* (G.H. Weber) P.M. Jørg. & S. Ekman (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Pannaria brunnea* α *genuina*', 1895: 122 as *P. brunnea*; Murati 1992: 261 as *Pannaria pezizoides*)
- Protoparmelia badia* (Hoffm.) Hafellner (Gallé 1935: 266 as *Lecanora badia*, 1975: 292 as *L. badia*; Murati 1993: 134; Dimović 2003: 145 as *L. badia*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Protoparmeliopsis muralis* (Schreb.) M. Choisy (Simić 1892: 451 as *Placodium saxicolum*, 1895: 123 & 147 as *P. saxicolum*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170 as *Lecanora saxicola*; Gallé 1935: 267 as *L. saxicola*; Servít 1934: 142 as *Lecanora muralis*, 1935: 79 as *L. muralis*; Soška 1949: 111 as *P. saxicolum*; Kušan 1953: 396 as *Lecanora albomarginata*, 404-405 as *L. muralis*; Krause & Klement 1958: 7 as *P. saxicolum*; Murati 1993: 142 as *L. muralis*; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20 as *L. muralis*; Stamenković 1998: 72 as *L. muralis*; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Pseudevernia furfuracea* (L.) Zopf (Simić 1892: 451 as *Evernia furfuracea*, 1895: 115 as *E. furfuracea*, 1897: 6 as *E. furfuracea*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 171 as *Parmelia furfuracea*; Gallé 1935: 269 as *E. furfuracea*, 1975: 293; Kušan 1936: 193 as *P. furfuracea*, 1953: 432-433 as *P. furfuracea*; Soška 1949: 110 as *E. furfuracea*; Gajić 1988: 69 as *E. furfuracea*, 1989: 97 as *E. furfuracea*; Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 315; Savić 1996: 60; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 145)
- Pseudosagedia aenea* (Wallr.) Hafellner & Kalb (Servít 1934: 125 as *Porina carpineae*; Kušan 1953: 91 as *Porina chlorotica* var. *carpineae*; Murati 1993: 203 as *Porina aenea*)
- Pseudosagedia chlorotica* (Ach.) Hafellner & Kalb (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Psora decipiens* (Hedw.) Hoffm. (Servít 1934: 135 as *Lecidea decipiens*; Kušan 1953: 243 as *L. decipiens*; Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 317)
- Psora testacea* Hoffm. (Servít 1935: 76 as *Lecidea testacea*; Kušan 1953: 247 as *L. testacea*; Murati 1992: 160 as *Chrysozpora testacea*, 314 as *Protoblastenia testacea*)
- Psora vallesiaca* (Schaer.) Timdal (Servít 1935: 76 as *Lecidea deceptoria*; Kušan 1953: 242 as *L. deceptoria*; Murati 1992: 316 as *P. albilabra*)
- Psorotichia myriospora* Zahlbr. (Servít 1937: 7 as *Gonohymenia myriospora*; Kušan 1953: 151 as *G. myriospora*; Murati 1992: 199 as *G. myriospora*)
- Psorotichia schaeferi* (A. Massal.) Arnold (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161; Kušan 1953: 152; Murati 1993: 208 as *Collemopsis schaeferi*; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 328; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Punctelia subrudecta* (Nyl.) Krog (Servít 1934: 145 as *Parmelia borrieri*; Gallé 1935: 268 as *Parmelia dubia*, 1975: 293 as '*Parmelia subrudecta* var. *deliblatensis* Gyeln.>'; Soška 1949: 110 as *P. dubia* var. *deliblatensis* Gyeln.; Kušan 1953: 448 as *P. borrieri*; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185 as *P. dubia*; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111 as *P. dubia*; Gajić 1983: 40 as *P. dubia*; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92 as *P. dubia*; Murati 1993: 185; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178 as *P. dubia*; Savić 1998: 339; Szabados 1998: 60 as *Parmelia subrudecta*; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2003: 145 as *P. subrudecta*)
- Pycnora praestabilis* (Nyl.) Hafellner (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Pycnothelia papillaria* (Ehrh.) Dufour (Simić 1892: 451 as *Cladonia papillaria*, 1895: 113 as *C. papillaria*; Murati 1993: 274).
- Pyrenocollema monense* (Wheldon) Coppins (Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Pyrenula coryli* A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 125; Kušan 1953: 95; Murati 1992: 320 as *Mycopyprenula coryli*)
- Pyrenula laevigata* (Pers.) Arnold (Servít 1934: 125; Kušan 1953: 96; Murati 1992: 320)
- Pyrenula nitida* (Weigel) Ach. (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 137, 1900: 47; Katić 1904: 4 as 'var. *major* Rbh.', 1907: 14, 1910: 40; Murati 1992: 320; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 145; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Pyrenula nitidella* (Flörke ex Schaer.) Müll. Arg. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 161; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 97 as *P. nitida* var. *nitidella*; Murati 1992: 321)
- Ramalina calicaris* (L.) Fr. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 115; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174; Kušan 1953: 476; Gallé 1935: 269, 1975: 294; Murati 1992: 323)
- Ramalina capitata* (Ach.) Nyl. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174 as *R. strepsilis*; Kušan 1953: 483 as *R. strepsilis*; Murati 1992: 324; Savić 1996: 60)
- Ramalina deliblatensis* Gyeln. (Soška 1949: 111; Gallé 1975: 294; Gajić 1983: 40)
- Ramalina farinacea* (L.) Ach. (Gallé 1935: 269, 1975: 294; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111; Murati 1992: 325; Savić 1996: 60; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 146; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Ramalina fastigiata* (Pers.) Ach. (Katić 1910: 40; Gallé 1975: 294; Murati 1992: 326; Savić 1996: 60; Dimović 2003: 146)
- Ramalina fraxinea* (L.) Ach. (Simić 1896: 9; Katić 1910: 40; Servít 1934: 147; Gallé 1935: 269, 1975: 294; Soška 1949: 111; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111; Gajić 1983: 40; Gajić & Karadžić

- 1991: 66; Murati 1992: 326; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 146; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Ramalina obtusata* (Arnold) Bitter (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174 as *R. baltica*; Kušan 1953: 475 as *R. baltica*; Murati 1992: 327; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104).
- Note: From the literature sources, it has not been possible to separate *R. baltica* from *R. obtusata*.
- Ramalina pollinaria* (Westr.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174; Servít 1934: 147, 1935: 81; Kušan 1953: 482; Gallé 1935: 269, 1975: 294; Murati 1992: 327; Kojić 2002: 143, 703 as *R. intermedia*)
- Ramalina polymorpha* (Lilj.) Ach. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 115; Soška 1949: 111; Murati 1990: 50, 1992: 327)
- Rhizocarpon badioatrum* (Flörke ex Spreng.) Th. Fr. (Simić 1892: 452 as 'Buellia badioatra Flk. α vulgaris', 1895: 131 as *B. badioatra*; Murati 1992: 332; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 146)
- Rhizocarpon disporum* (Nägeli ex Hepp) Müll. Arg. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166 as *R. montagnei*; Kušan 1953: 281; Poelt 1975: 429; Murati 1992: 332)
- Rhizocarpon distinctum* Th. Fr. (Servít 1935: 76 as *R. ambiguum*; Kušan 1953: 278 as *R. ambiguum*; Feuerer 1991: 93; Murati 1992: 333; Savić *et al.* 2006: 104)
- Rhizocarpon geminatum* Körb. (Servít 1935: 76; Murati 1990: 50; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rhizocarpon geographicum* s. lat. (Simić 1895: 131 & 147, 1897: 7, 1898: 15; Katić 1910: 39; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166; Servít 1935: 77; Soška 1949: 109; Kušan 1953: 282; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Murati 1990: 51, 1992: 333; Savić 1996: 60; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 146; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Rhizocarpon lecanorinum* Anders (Simić 1892: 452 as 'α atrovirens Fw. '; Dimović 2001: 111; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rhizocarpon obscuratum* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Feuerer 1991: 145; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rhizocarpon oederi* (Weber) Körb. (Murati 1992: 335)
- Rhizocarpon petraeum* (Wulfen) A. Massal. (Simić 1892: 452 as 'α vulgare', 1895: 132, 1900: 47; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 166 as *R. concentricum*; Kušan 1953: 280 as *R. concentricum*; Murati 1992: 332 as *R. concentricum*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rhizocarpon reductum* Th. Fr. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rhizocarpon simillimum* (Anzi) Lettau (Servít 1935: 77; Kušan 1953: 278; Murati 1992: 336)
- Rhizocarpon umbilicatum* (Ramond) Flagey (Servít 1935: 76 as *R. calcareum*; Kušan 1953: 279 as *R. calcareum*; Murati 1992: 336; Kojić 2002: 143)
- Rhizocarpon viridiatrum* (Wulfen) Körb. (Poelt 1975: 429; Murati 1990: 51, 1992: 336; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rhizoplaca melanophthalma* (DC.) Leuckert & Poelt (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rinodina albana* (A. Massal.) A. Massal. (Magnusson 1947: 248)
- Rinodina archaea* (Ach.) Arnold (Murati 1993: 214)
- Rinodina bischoffii* (Hepp) A. Massal. (Servít 1934: 157; Kušan 1953: 556; Murati 1993: 214; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rinodina calcarea* (Arnold) Arnold (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rinodina dubyana* (Hepp) J. Steiner (Servít 1935: 86 as *R. mediterranea*; Kušan 1953: 560 as *R. mediterranea*)
- Rinodina exigua* (Ach.) Gray (Simić 1892: 451 as 'R. metabolica var. exigua', 1895: 124; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Kušan 1953: 560; Murati 1993: 218; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rinodina gennarii* Bagl. (Gallé 1975: 295 as *R. salina*; Murati 1993: 218; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Rinodina immersa* (Körb.) Zahlbr. (Servít 1935: 85; Kušan 1953: 556 as *R. bischoffii* var. *immersa*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Rinodina lecanorina* (A. Massal.) A. Massal. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177 as *R. ocellata*; Servít 1934: 158 as *R. ocellata*; Kušan 1953: 561 as *R. ocellata*; Mayrhofer *et al.* 1990: 345; Murati 1993: 219)
- Rinodina luridata* (Körb.) H. Mayrhofer, Scheid. & Sheard (Mayrhofer *et al.* 1990: 352)
- Rinodina milvina* (Wahlenb.) Th. Fr. (Katić 1910: 38 as 'R. sophodes Ach. var. milvina (Whlbg.)'; Kušan 1936: 199, 1953: 560; Mayrhofer 1984: 437; Murati 1993: 219)
- Rinodina oxydata* (A. Massal.) A. Massal. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177 as *R. discolor*, 178 as 'R. discolor var. candida'; Kušan 1953: 559 as *R. discolor*; Murati 1990: 51, 1993: 220)
- Rinodina polyspora* Th. Fr. (Servít 1934: 158; Magnusson 1947: 281; Kušan 1953: 562; Murati 1993: 221)
- Rinodina pyrina* (Ach.) Arnold (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Servít 1934: 158; Gallé 1935: 270; Magnusson 1947: 219; Gallé 1975: 295; Kušan 1953: 562; Murati 1993: 221)
- Rinodina rinodinooides* (Anzi) H. Mayrhofer & Scheidegger (Mayrhofer *et al.* 1992: 455)
- Rinodina sophodes* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Servít 1935: 86; Magnusson 1947: 224; Kušan 1953: 562; Murati 1993: 222)
- Rinodina teichophila* (Nyl.) Arnold (Murati 1990: 51, 1993: 223)
- Rinodinella controversa* (A. Massal.) H. Mayrhofer & Poelt (Servít 1935: 85 as *R. crustulata*; Kušan 1953: 558 as *R. crustulata*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Sarcogyne clavus* (DC.) Kremp. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *Biatorella clavus*; Kušan 1953: 324; Murati 1992: 341)
- Sarcogyne privigna* (Ach.) A. Massal. (Servít 1935: 77 as *Biatorella privigna*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Sarcogyne regularis* Körb. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *Biatorella pruinosa*; Servít 1934: 140 as *B. pruinosa*; Kušan 1953: 325-326 as *S. pruinosa*; Murati 1992: 342 as *S. pruinosa*; Kojić 2002: 144 as *S. pruinosa*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)

- Schaereria fuscocinerea* (Nyl.) Clauzade & Cl. Roux (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Sclerophora peronella* (Ach.) Tibell (Kušan 1953: 105 as *Coniocybe hyalinella*; Murati 1993: 105)
- Scoliciosporum chlorococcum* (Graewe ex Stenh.) Vězda (Murati 1992: 343; Savić 1998: 339)
- Scoliciosporum sarothamni* (Vain.) Vězda (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Scoliciosporum umbrinum* (Ach.) Arnold (Murati 1990: 51; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Solenopsora candicans* (Dicks.) J. Steiner (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Solorina saccata* (L.) Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 163; Servít 1934: 132, 1935: 76; Kušan 1953: 201; Murati 1992: 344)
- Solorina spongiosa* (Sm.) Anzi (Murati 1992: 345)
- Sphaerophorus fragilis* (L.) Pers. (Savić 1996: 60)
- Sphaerophorus globosus* (Huds.) Vain. (Simić 1895: 135 as *S. coralloides*; Savić 1996: 61)
- Spilonema paradoxum* Bornet (Murati 1990: 51)
- Squamarina cartilaginea* (With.) P. James (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170 as *Lecanora crassa*; Servít 1934: 142 as *L. crassa*, 1935: 78 as *L. crassa*; Kušan 1953: 398-399 as *L. crassa*; Poelt & Krüger 1970: 193 as *S. crassa*; Murati 1992: 349; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Squamarina gypsacea* (Sm.) Poelt (Tatić & Veljović 1982: 70; Murati 1992: 350)
- Squamarina lamarckii* (DC.) Poelt (Servít 1935: 79 as *Lecanora lamarckii*; Kušan 1953: 402 as *L. lamarckii*; Murati 1992: 350)
- Squamarina lentigera* (Weber) Poelt (Soška 1949: 110 as *Lecanora lentigera*; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185 as *L. lentigera*; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 111 as *L. lentigera*; Gallé 1975: 292; Gajić 1983: 39 as *L. lentigera*)
- Squamarina serpentina* Poelt (Poelt 1975: 426)
- Staurothele ambrosiana* (A. Massal.) Zschacke (Murati 1993: 229)
- Staurothele caesia* (Arnold) Arnold (Servít 1935: 74; Kušan 1953: 63; Murati 1993: 229; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Staurothele frustulenta* Vain. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 160 as '*S. catalepta* f. *spadicea*'; Kušan 1953: 62 as *S. catalepta*; Gallé 1966: 29; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Staurothele guestphalica* (J. Lahm ex Körb.) Arnold (Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Stereocaulon alpinum* Laurer (Savić 1996: 61)
- Synalissa symphorea* (Ach.) Nyl. (Servít 1935: 75; Kušan 1953: 150; Murati 1992: 355; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20)
- Tephromela atra* (Huds.) Hafellner (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Lecanora atra* α *vulgaris*', 1895: 125 as *L. atra*; Katić 1907: 13 as '*L. atra* var. *vulgaris* Kbr.', 1910: 39 as *L. atra*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 170 as *L. atra*; Servít 1935: 78 as *L. atra*; Kušan 1953: 373 as *L. atra*; Gallé 1975: 292 as *L. atra*; Tatić & Veljović 1982: 70 as *L. atra*; Murati 1990: 49 as *L. atra*, 1993: 133; Dimović 2001: 109 as *L. atra*, 2003: 145 as *L. atra*)
- Tephromela grumosa* (Pers.) Hafellner & Cl. Roux (Murati 1990: 49 as '*Lecanora grumosa* (Pers.) Röhl. '; Savić *et al.* 2006: 105)
- Thamnomia vermicularis* (Sw.) Schaer. (Mišić *et al.* 1978: 332 & 338; Murati 1992: 356; Savić 1996: 61)
- Thelidium acrotellum* Arnold (Servít 1934: 123; Kušan 1953: 56)
- Thelidium decipiens* (Nyl.) Kremp. (Servít 1935: 74; Kušan 1953: 55; Murati 1993: 234)
- Thelidium papulare* (Fr.) Arnold (Zschacke 1934: 406; Kušan 1953: 58; Murati 1993: 236)
- Thelocarpon laureri* (Flot.) Nyl. (Szabados 1998: 60)
- Thelotrema lepadinum* (Ach.) Ach. (Dimović & Lökös 2003: 53)
- Thrombium epigaeum* (Pers.) Wallr. (Gallé 1935: 265, 1975: 290)
- Thyrea confusa* Henssen (Servít 1934: 130 as *Th. pulvinata*; Kušan 1953: 155 as *Th. pulvinata*; Murati 1993: 238 as *Th. pulvinata*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Thyrea girardii* (Du Rietz & Mont.) Bagl. & Carestia (Servít 1934: 129; Kušan 1953: 154; Murati 1993: 238)
- Toninia alutacea* (Anzi) Jatta (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165 as *T. intermedia*; Kušan 1953: 273 as *T. intermedia*; Murati 1992: 364)
- Toninia candida* (Weber) Th. Fr. (Soška 1949: 109; Murati 1992: 365; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20)
- Toninia cinereovirens* (Schaer.) A. Massal. (Timdal 1991: 55)
- Toninia diffracta* (A. Massal.) Zahlbr. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Toninia rosulata* (Anzi) H. Olivier (Dimović 2003: 146)
- Toninia sedifolia* (Scop.) Timdal (Simić 1892: 452 as *Thalloidima vesiculare*, 1895: 128 as *T. vesiculare*, 1897: 7 as *T. vesiculare*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165 as *Toninia caeruleonigricans*; Servít 1934: 139 as *T. caeruleonigricans*, 1935: 76 as *T. caeruleonigricans*; Kušan 1953: 271-272 as *T. caeruleonigricans*; Gallé 1975: 291 as *T. caeruleonigricans*)

- f. dispersum* (Nyl.) Szat.; Murati 1990: 51 as *T. caeruleonigricans*, 1992: 364 as *T. caeruleonigricans*)
- Toninia tumidula* (Sm.) Zahlbr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165 as *T. mesenteriformis*; Kušan 1953: 274; Murati 1992: 369)
- Trapelia coarctata* (Sm.) M. Choisy (Katić 1907: 14 as '*Biatora coarctata* (Sm.) var. *elachista* Th. Fr.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 165 as *Lecideia coarctata* var. *elachista*; Servít 1934: 141 as *Lecanora coarctata*; Kušan 1953: 379 as *Lecanora coarctata*; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Trapelia involuta* (Taylor) Hertel (Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Trapelia obtegens* (Th. Fr.) Hertel (Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Trapeliopsis flexuosa* (Fr.) Coppins & P. James (Dimović & Lököš 2003: 53; Seaward & John 2005: 67)
- Trapeliopsis granulosa* (Hoffm.) Lumbsch (Simić 1892: 452 as '*Biatora decolorans* Hoffm.', 1895: 129 as *B. decolorans*; Seaward & John 2005: 67; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Trapeliopsis wallrothii* (Flörke ex Spreng.) Hertel & Gotth. Schneid. (Murati 1992: 236)
- Tuckermanopsis chlorophylla* (Willd.) Hale (Dimović 2001: 109 as *Cetraria chlorophylla*)
- Tuckneraria laureri* (Kremp.) Randle & A. Thell (Murati 1990: 48 as *Cetraria laureri*)
- Umbilicaria crustulosa* (Ach.) Frey (Murati 1992: 370; Dimović 2003: 146)
- Umbilicaria cylindrica* (L.) Delise ex Duby (Katić 1907: 13 as *Gyrophora cylindrica*; Kušan 1953: 320; Murati 1992: 371; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Umbilicaria deusta* (L.) Baumg. (Kušan 1936: 186, 1953: 321; Murati 1992: 371; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Umbilicaria grisea* Hoffm. (Murati 1990: 51, 1992: 371; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 67)
- Umbilicaria hirsuta* (Sw. ex Westr.) Hoffm. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 167 as *Gyrophora hirsuta*; Kušan 1953: 320; Murati 1992: 372; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Umbilicaria nylanderiana* (Zahlbr.) H. Magn. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Usnea balcanica* Bystrek (Murati 1993: 243)
- Usnea barbata* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Simić 1892: 450, 1895: 114; Kušan 1953: 486; Murati 1993: 244; Dimović 2003: 146)
- Usnea ceratina* Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175; Kušan 1936: 197, 1953: 484; Murati 1993: 245)
- Usnea flipendula* Stirt. (Katić 1907: 12 as '*Usnea barbata* Fr. var. *dasyypoga* Fr.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175 as *U. dasyypoga*; Kušan 1953: 485 as *U. dasyypoga*; Gajić 1989: 97 as *U. dasyypoga*; Murati 1990: 51, 1993: 246; Savić 1996: 61)
- Usnea glabrescens* (Nyl. ex Vain.) Vain. (Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Usnea hirta* (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. (Katić 1907: 12 as '*Usnea barbata* Fr. var. *hirta* Fr.>'; Soška 1949: 111; Kušan 1953: 486; Gallé 1975: 294; Murati 1993: 249; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 146)
- Usnea lapponica* Vain. (Murati 1993: 250)
- Usnea longissima* Ach. (Gajić 1988: 69; Murati 1993: 250)
- Usnea scabrata* Nyl. (Murati 1990: 51)
- Usnea subfloridana* Stirt. (Simić 1892: 450 as *U. florida*, 1895: 114 as '*U. barbata* var. *florida*', 1896: 9 as '*U. barbata* L. α *florida*'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 174 as *U. florida*, 175 as '*U. florida* v. *sorediifera* Arn.>'; Kušan 1953: 486 as *U. florida*; Gajić 1988: 69 as *U. florida*; Murati 1990: 51, 1993: 247 as *U. florida*; Savić 1996: 61 as *U. florida*; Dimović 2001: 111 as *U. florida*, 2003: 146 as *U. florida*)
- Verrucaria aquatilis* Mudd (Servít 1934: 120; Kušan 1953: 47; Murati 1993: 259)
- Verrucaria caerulea* DC. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 160 as *V. glaucina*; Kušan 1953: 50 as *V. glaucina*; Murati 1993: 264 as *V. glaucina*; Seaward & John 2005: 66; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Verrucaria calciseda* auct. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 159; Zschacke 1934: 84; Servít 1935: 73; Kušan 1953: 25-26; Gallé 1966: 29, 1975: 290; Murati 1993: 261; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Verrucaria dolosa* Hepp (Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)
- Verrucaria dufourii* DC. (Servít 1935: 74; Kušan 1953: 41; Murati 1993: 262)
- Verrucaria fuscella* (Turner) Winch (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 136; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 159; Servít 1936: 256 as *V. griseoatra*; Kušan 1953: 50 as *V. nigricans*, 51 as *V. griseoatra*)
- Verrucaria hochstetteri* Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 159 as *V. arnoldii*; Kušan 1953: 22 as *V. arnoldii*)
- Verrucaria hydrela* Ach. (Servít 1934: 121 as *V. denudata*; Kušan 1953: 47 as *V. denudata*; Murati 1993: 265)
- Verrucaria limborioides* (A. Massal.) Clauzade & Cl. Roux (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 159 as '*V. sphinctrina* v. *alocyza* (Arn.) Szatala'; Kušan 1953: 36 as '*Verrucaria parmigera* v. *alociza*')
- Verrucaria muralis* Ach. (Simić 1892: 453 as *V. muralis*, *V. rupestris*, 1895: 136 as *V. muralis*, *V. rupestris*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 159 as *V. rupestris*; Kušan 1953: 40 as *V. rupestris*; Krause & Klement 1958: 7 as *V. rupestris*; Gallé 1966: 29, 1975: 290; Murati 1993: 268; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Verrucaria nigrescens* Pers. (Simić 1892: 453 as '*V. fuscoatra* Wallr. β *controversa* Mass.>'; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 159; Servít 1934: 121 as *V. controversa*, 1935: 74 as *V. controversa*; Gallé 1935: 265, 1966: 29, 1975: 290 as *V. fusca*; Kušan 1953: 48 as *V. controversa*, 53; Krause & Klement 1958: 7; Murati 1993: 268; Seaward & John 2005: 66)
- Verrucaria rtanjensis* Servít (Servít 1949: 42)
- Verrucaria umbrosa* (A. Massal.) Trevis. (Zschacke, 1934: 74; Kušan 1953: 23; Murati 1993: 271)

Vulpicida pinastri (Scop.) J.-E. Mattsson & M.J. Lai (Murati 1990: 48 as *Cetraria pinastri*; Savić 1996: 57)

Xanthoparmelia conspersa (Ehrh. ex Ach.) Hale (Simić 1892: 451 as '*Imbricaria conspersa* Ehrh.', 1895: 120 & 146 as *Parmelia conspersa*, 1897: 7 as *P. conspersa*; Katić 1903: 4 as *P. conspersa*; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 171 as *P. conspersa*; Servít 1935: 80 as *P. isidiata*; Kušan 1953: 446-447 as *P. conspersa*; Soška 1949: 110 as *P. conspersa*; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 330 as *P. conspersa*; Murati 1993: 176; Zlatković & Randelović 1996: 68; Dimović 2001: 110 as *P. conspersa*, 2003: 145 as *P. conspersa*)

Xanthoparmelia somloënsis (Gyeln.) Hale (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as '*Parmelia conspersa* f. *stenophylla*'; Kušan 1953: 434 as *Parmelia molliuscula*; Krause & Klement 1958: 7 as *P. molliuscula*; Murati 1993: 184; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)

Xanthoparmelia sublaevis (Cout.) Hale (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 172 as *Parmelia conspersa* f. *hypoclista*)

Xanthoparmelia tinctina (Maheu & A. Gillet) Hale (Anonymous 1979: 28 as *Parmelia tinctina*)

Xanthoria calcicola Oxner (Gallé 1975: 294 as *X. aureola* var. *aureola*)

Xanthoria candelaria (L.) Th. Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Kušan 1953: 538; Gallé 1975: 294; Murati 1992: 376; Savić 1998: 339; Seaward & John 2005: 67; Savić *et al.* 2006: 106)

Xanthoria elegans (Link) Th. Fr. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176 as *Caloplaca elegans*; Kušan 1953: 534 as *C. elegans*; Tatić & Veljović 1982: 70 as *C. elegans*; Murati 1992: 376; Kojić 2002: 144; Dimović 2003: 146)

Xanthoria fallax (Hepp) Arnold (Gallé 1975: 294; Murati 1992: 376; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Szabados 1998: 60)

Xanthoria parietina (L.) Th. Fr. (Simić 1892: 451, 1895: 121 & 146, 1900: 47; Katić 1910: 38; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 176; Servít 1934: 157; Soška 1949: 111 (? f. *aurantiaca*); Kušan 1953: 540 & 543; Marinović & Bata 1967: 185; Marinović & Stanković 1972: 112; Gallé 1974: 39, 1975: 294; Bejtullahu *et al.* 1983: 330; Gajić 1983: 41, 1986: 53; Gajić & Karadžić 1991: 66; Murati 1992: 377; Milić & Blaženčić 1993: 92; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Randelović 1995: 20; Randelović & Kujundžić 1995: 20; Stamenković 1995: 44, 1998: 72; Savić 1996: 61, 1998: 337; Szabados 1998: 60; Todorović 1998: 75; Dimović 2001: 111, 2003: 146; Kojić 2002: 144; Seaward & John 2005: 67)

Xanthoria polycarpa (Hoffm.) Rieber (Murati 1992: 377)

Xanthoria soredata (Vain.) Poelt (Servít 1934: 156 as *Caloplaca soredata*; Kušan 1953: 536 as *C. soredata*; Murati 1992: 377)

Xylographa parallela (Ach. : Fr.) Fr. (Murati 1990: 51 as *X. abietina*)

Xylographa vitiligo (Ach.) J.R. Laundon (Murati 1990: 51)

List of synonyms

Alectoria degenii Szatala = *Bryoria capillaris*
Alectoria implexa auct. = *Bryoria capillaris*
Alectoria jubata var. *implexa* auct. = *Bryoria capillaris*
Alectoria jubata var. *prolixa* (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Bryoria fuscescens*
Alectoria jubata auct. = *Bryoria fuscescens*

Amphiloma murorum (Hoffm.) Körb. = *Caloplaca saxicola*

Anaptychia ciliaris var. *crinalis* Schleich. = *Anaptychia crinalis*

Arthonia astroidea Ach. = *Arthonia radiata*
Arthonia vulgaris Schaer. = *Arthonia radiata*

Arthopyrenia alba (Schrad.) Zahlbr. = *Acrocordia gemmata*
Arthopyrenia analepta auct. = *Naetrocymbe punctiformis*
Arthopyrenia fallax (Nyl.) Arnold = *Arthopyrenia analepta*
Arthopyrenia fraxinii A. Massal. = *Naetrocymbe fraxinii*
Arthopyrenia lapponina Anzi = *Arthopyrenia analepta*
Arthopyrenia punctiformis (Pers.) A. Massal. = *Naetrocymbe punctiformis*
Arthopyrenia saxicola. A. Massal. = *Naetrocymbe saxicola*

Arthothelium ruanum (A. Massal.) Körb. = *Arthonia ruana*

Aspicilia contorta subsp. *hoffmanniana* S. Ekman & Fröberg = *Aspicilia hoffmannii*
Aspicilia contorta var. *calcarea* (L.) Körb. = *Aspicilia contorta*
Aspicilia gibbosa auct. = *Aspicilia caesiocinerea*
Aspicilia radiosa (Hoffm.) Poelt & Leuckert = *Lobothallia radiosa*
Aspicilia verrucosa (Ach.) Körb. = *Megaspora verrucosa*

Bacidia acclinis (Flot.) Zahlbr. = *Arthrosporium populum*
Bacidia fusca (A. Massal.) Du Reitz = *Mycobilimbia tetramera*
Bacidia hegetschweileri auct. non (Hepp) Vain. = *Bacidia vermifera*
Bacidia luteola auct. = *Bacidia rubella*
Bacidia muscorum (Sw.) Mudd = *Bacidia bagliettoana*
Bacidia naegelii (Hepp) Zahlbr. = *Lecania naegelii*
Bacidia populum (A. Massal.) Trevis. = *Arthrosporium populum*
Bacidia sabuletorum (Schreb.) Lettau = *Myxobilimbia sabuletorum*
Bacidia sphaeroides (Dicks.) Körb. = *Mycobilimbia pilularis*
Bacidia trisepta (Hellb.) Zahlbr. = *Micarea peliocarpa*

Baeomyces roseus Pers. = *Dibaeis baeomyces*

Biatora decolorans auct. = *Trapeliopsis granulosa*
Biatora pilularis (Körb.) Hepp = *Mycobilimbia pilularis*

- Biatora rivulosa* (Ach.) Fr. = *Fuscidea cyathoides*
Biatora uliginosa (Schrad.) Fr. = *Placynthiella uliginosa*
- Biatorella clavus* (DC.) Th. Fr. = *Sarcogyne clavus*
Biatorella ochrophora (Nyl.) Arnold = *Piccolia ochrophora*
Biatorella privigna (Ach.) Sandst. = *Sarcogyne privigna*
Biatorella pruinosa auct. = *Sarcogyne regularis*
Biatorella simplex (Davies) Branth & Rostr. = *Polysporina simplex*
- Bilimbia sphaeroides* var. *muscorum* (Ach.) Anzi = *Bacidia bagliettoana*
- Blastenia ochracea* (Schaer.) Trevis. = *Caloplaca ochracea*
- Bryopogon jubatum* L. = *Bryoria fuscescens*
Bryopogon jubatus var. *prolixum* (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Bryoria fuscescens*
- Bryoria jubata* auct. = *Bryoria fuscescens*
Bryoria proluxa (Ach.) Nyl. = *Bryoria fuscescens*
- Buellia alboatra* (Hoffm.) Th. Fr. = *Diplotomma alboatrum*
Buellia ambigua (Ach.) Malme = *Diplotomma alboatrum*
Buellia badioatra (Flörke ex Spreng.) Körb. = *Rhizocarpon badioatrum*
Buellia epipolia (Ach.) Mong. = *Diplotomma alboatrum*
Buellia epipolia var. *venusta* (Körb.) Th. Fr. = *Diplotomma venustum*
Buellia myricarpa (DC.) De Not. = *Amandinea punctata*
Buellia punctata (Hoffm.) A. Massal. = *Amandinea punctata*
Buellia punctiformis (Hoffm.) A. Massal. = *Amandinea punctata*
Buellia zahlbruckneri J. Steiner = *Buellia erubescens*
- Callophisma aurantiacum* auct. = *Caloplaca flavorubescens*
Callophisma cerinum (Hedw.) De Not. = *Caloplaca cerina*
Callophisma luteoalbum (Turner) A. Massal. = *Caloplaca luteoalba*
Callophisma vitellinum (Hoffm.) Bagl. = *Candelariella vitellina*
- Caloplaca agardhiana* f. *albopruinosa* (Arnold) J. Steiner = *Caloplaca alociza*
Caloplaca aurantiaca auct. = *Caloplaca flavorubescens*
Caloplaca boulyi (Zahlbr.) M. Steiner & Poelt = *Caloplaca lobulata*
Caloplaca callophisma (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Caloplaca aurantia*
Caloplaca cinnamomea (Th. Fr.) H. Olivier = *Caloplaca ammiospila*
Caloplaca cerina var. *muscorum* (A. Massal.) M. Choisy & Werner = *Caloplaca cerina*
Caloplaca cinnamomea (Th. Fr.) H. Olivier = *Caloplaca ammiospila*
Caloplaca congregiens auct. = *Caloplaca grimmiae*
Caloplaca dolomiticola (Hue) Zahlbr. = *Caloplaca velana*
- Caloplaca elegans* (Link.) Th. Fr. = *Xanthoria elegans*
Caloplaca festiva (Ach.) Zwackh = *Caloplaca crenularia*
Caloplaca fuscoatra auct. = *Caloplaca aractina*
Caloplaca gilva (Hoffm.) Zahlbr. = *Caloplaca cerina*
Caloplaca heppiana (Müll. Arg.) Zahlbr. = *Caloplaca flavescens*
Caloplaca lithophila H. Magn. = *Caloplaca holocarpa*
Caloplaca murorum (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Caloplaca saxicola*
Caloplaca placidia (A. Massal.) J. Steiner = *Caloplaca velana*
Caloplaca pruinosa (Körb.) Zahlbr. = *Fulgensia pruinosa*
Caloplaca pyracea (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Caloplaca holocarpa*
Caloplaca schistidii (Anzi) Zahlbr. = *Fulgensia schistidii*
Caloplaca solediata (Vain.) Du Rietz = *Xanthoria solediata*
Caloplaca subsimilis Th. Fr. = *Candelariella aurella*
Caloplaca viridirufa auct. = *Caloplaca aractina*
- Candelaria vulgaris* A. Massal. = *Candelaria concolor*
- Candelariella granulata* (Schaer.) Zahlbr. = *Candelariella medians*
Candelariella vitellina var. *xanthostigna* (Ach.) Elenkin = *Candelariella xanthostigma*
- Catapyrenium rufescens* (Ach.) Breuss = *Placidium rufescens*
Catapyrenium squamulosum (Ach.) Breuss = *Placidium squamulosum*
- Catillaria globulosa* (Flörke) Th. Fr. = *Lecania hyalina*
Catillaria prasina (Fr.) Th. Fr. = *Micarea prasina*
Catillaria pulverea (Borrer) Lettau = *Megalaria pulverea*
- Cetraria aculeata* var. *alpina* Schaer. = *Cetraria muricata*
Cetraria chlorophylla (Willd.) Vain. = *Tuckermanopsis chlorophylla*
Cetraria cucullata (Bellardi) Ach. = *Flavocetraria cucullata*
Cetraria glauca (L.) Ach. = *Platismatia glauca*
Cetraria islandica var. *crispa* Ach. = *Cetraria ericetorum*
Cetraria islandica var. *tenuifolia* (Retz.) Vain. = *Cetraria ericetorum*
Cetraria laureri Kremp. = *Tuckneraria laureri*
Cetraria nivalis (L.) Ach. = *Flavocetraria nivalis*
Cetraria pinastri (Scop.) Ach. = *Vulpicida pinastri*
- Chaenotheca nudiuscula* auct. = *Chaenotheca xyloxena*
- Chrysozora testacea* (Hoffm.) M. Choisy = *Psora testacea*
- Cladonia alcornis* (Lightf.) Fr. = *Cladonia foliacea*
Cladonia bacillaris Genth = *Cladonia macilenta*
Cladonia cornutoradiata (Coem.) Sandst. = *Cladonia subulata*
Cladonia degenerans (Flörke) Spreng = *Cladonia phyllophora*
Cladonia delicata auct. = *Cladonia parasitica*
Cladonia endiviaefolia auct. = *Cladonia convoluta*
Cladonia foliacea var. *convoluta* (Lam.) Vain. = *Cladonia convoluta*

- Cladonia major* (K.G. Hagen) Sandst. = *Cladonia fimbriata*
Cladonia minor (K.G. Hagen) Szatala = *Cladonia fimbriata*
Cladonia papillaria (Ehrh.) Hoffm. = *Pycnothelia papillaria*
Cladonia pyxidata var. *chlorophaea* (Flörke ex Sommerf.)
 Flörke = *Cladonia chlorophaea*
Cladonia pyxidata var. *pocillum* (Ach.) Schaer. = *Cladonia pocillum*
- Coelocaulon aculeatum* (Schreb.) Link = *Cetraria aculeata*
- Collema cheileum* (Ach.) Ach. = *Collema crispum*
Collema furvum (Ach.) DC. = *Collema fuscovirens*
Collema glaucescens Hoffm. = *Collema limosum*
Collema granosum auct. = *Collema auriforme*
Collema multifidum (Scop.) Rabenh. = *Collema cristatum*
Collema pulposum (Bernh. ex Schaer.) Ach. = *Collema tenax*
Collema rupestre (Sw.) Rabenh. = *Collema flaccidum*
- Collemopsis schaeereri* (A. Massal.) Cromb. = *Psorotichia schaeereri*
- Coniocybe furfuracea* (L.) Ach. = *Chaenotheca furfuracea*
Coniocybe hyalinella Nyl. = *Sclerophora peronella*
- Cornicularia aculeata* (Schreb.) Ach. = *Cetraria aculeata*
- Dermatocarpon hepaticum* auct. = *Placidium squamulosum*
Dermatocarpon intestiniforme (Körb.) Hasse = *Dermatocarpon miniatum*
Dermatocarpon monstrosum (Schaer.) Vain. = *Placocarpus schaeereri*
Dermatocarpon lachneum (Ach.) A.L. Sm. = *Placidium lachneum*
Dermatocarpon rufescens (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Placidium rufescens*
Dermatocarpon trachyticum (Hazsl.) Vain. = *Placopyrenium trachyticum*
- Diploschistes bryophilus* (Ach.) Zahlbr. = *Diploschistes muscorum*
- Diplotomma alboatrum* var. *epipolium* (Ach.) A. Massal. = *Diplotomma alboatrum*
- Endocarpon miniatum* (L.) Gaertn. = *Dermatocarpon miniatum*
Endocarpon pallidum auct. = *Endocarpum adscendens*
- Evernia furfuracea* (L.) W. Mann = *Pseudevernia furfuracea*
- Gasparrinia cirrochroa* (Ach.) Stein = *Caloplaca cirrochroa*
Gasparrinia decipiens (Arnold) Sydow. = *Caloplaca decipiens*
Gasparrinia murorum (Hoffm.) Tornab. = *Caloplaca saxicola*
- Gyrophora cilindrica* (L.) Ach. = *Umbilicaria cylindrica*
Gyrophora hirsuta (Sw. ex Westr.) Hoffm. = *Umbilicaria hirsuta*
- Haematomma ventosum* (L.) A. Massal. = *Ophioparma ventosa*
- Heppia guepinii* (Delise) Nyl. = *Peltula euploca*
- Icmadophila aeruginosa* (Scop.) Trevis. = *Icmadophila ericetorum*
- Imbricaria aleurites* Körb. = *Imshaugia aleurites*
Imbricaria caperata DC. = *Flavoparmelia caperata*
Imbricaria conspersa (Ehrh. ex Ach.) DC. = *Xanthoparmelia conspersa*
Imbricaria physodes (L.) Ach. = *Hypogymnia physodes*
Imbricaria saxatilis (L.) Körb. = *Parmelia saxatilis*
- Ionaspis cyrtaspis* auct. = *Hymenelia melanocarpa*
Ionaspis epulotica (Ach.) Arnold = *Hymenelia epulotica*
Ionaspis melanocarpa (Kremp.) Arnold = *Hymenelia melanocarpa*
- Lecania dimera* (Nyl.) Th. Fr. = *Lecania dubitans*
Lecania erysibe var. *rabenhorstii* (Hepp) Mudd = *Lecania rabenhorstii*
Lecania syringea (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Lecania fuscella*
- Lecanora albomarginata* (Nyl.) Cromb. = *Protoparmeliopsis muralis*
Lecanora alpina Sommerf. = *Bellemeria alpina*
Lecanora angulosa (Schreb.) Ach. = *Lecanora carpinea*
Lecanora atra (Huds.) Ach. = *Tephromela atra*
Lecanora badia (Hoffm.) Ach. = *Protoparmelia badia*
Lecanora calcarea (L.) Sommerf. = *Aspicilia calcarea*
Lecanora chlarona (Ach.) Nyl. = *Lecanora pulicaris*
Lecanora cinerea (L.) Sommerf. = *Aspicilia cinerea*
Lecanora coarctata (Sm.) Ach. = *Trapelia coarctata*
Lecanora coilocarpa auct. = *Lecanora pulicaris*
Lecanora contorta (Hoffm.) J. Steiner = *Aspicilia contorta*
Lecanora crassa (Huds.) Ach. = *Squamarina cartilaginea*
Lecanora crassula H. Magn. = *Lecanora chlarotera*
Lecanora demissa (Körb.) Zahlbr. = *Caloplaca demissa*
Lecanora farinosa (Flörke) Nyl. = *Aspicilia farinosa*
Lecanora galactina Ach. = *Lecanora albescens*
Lecanora gibbosa auct. = *Aspicilia caesiocinerea*
Lecanora grumosa (Pers.) Du Rietz = *Tephromela grumosa*
Lecanora hoffmannii (Ach.) Müll. Arg. = *Aspicilia hoffmannii*
Lecanora incusa (Flot.) Zahlbr. = *Caloplaca demissa*
Lecanora laevata (Ach.) Nyl. = *Aspicilia laevata*
Lecanora lamarckii (DC.) Poelt = *Squamarina lamarckii*
Lecanora lentigera (Weber) Ach. = *Squamarina lentigera*
Lecanora muralis (Schreb.) Rabenh. = *Protoparmeliopsis muralis*
Lecanora pallida (Schreb.) Rabenh. = *Lecanora albella*
Lecanora pallida var. *angulosa* (Schreb.) Rabenh. = *Lecanora carpinea*
Lecanora prevostii (Duby) Th. Fr. = *Hymenelia prevostii*
Lecanora radiosa (Hoffm.) Schaer. = *Lobothallia radiosa*

- Lecanora saxicola* (Pollich) Ach. = *Protoparmeliopsis muralis*
Lecanora subcircinata Nyl. = *Lobothallia radiosa*
Lecanora subfusca var. *allophana* Ach. = *Lecanora allophana*
Lecanora subfusca var. *margaritacea* Körb. = *Lecanora allophana*
Lecanora subfuscata H. Magn. = *Lecanora argentata*
Lecanora viridescens (A. Massal.) Müll. Arg. = *Aspicilia viridescens*
- Lecidea coarctata* (Sm.) Nyl. = *Trapelia coarctata*
Lecidea contigua (Hoffm.) Fr. = *Porpidia macrocarpa*
Lecidea crustulata (Ach.) Spreng. = *Porpidia crustulata*
Lecidea cyanea sensu Th. Fr. = *Lecidea tessellata*
Lecidea deceptoria Nyl. = *Psora vallesiacea*
Lecidea decipiens (Hedw.) Ach. = *Psora decipiens*
Lecidea declinans Nyl. = *Lecidea lapicida*
Lecidea elaeochroma (Ach.) Ach. = *Lecidella elaeochroma*
Lecidea fumosa (Hoffm.) Ach. = *Lecidea fuscoatra*
Lecidea glomerulosa (DC.) Steud. = *Lecidella euphorea*
Lecidea hypocrita A. Massal. = *Farnoldia hypocrita*
Lecidea incongrua Nyl. = *Lecidella stigmatea*
Lecidea insularis Nyl. = *Rimularia insularis*
Lecidea latypea Ach. = *Lecidea plana*
Lecidea latypiza auct. = *Lecidella carpathica*
Lecidea lithospersa Zahlbr. = *Farnoldia hypocrita*
Lecidea lurida Ach. = *Mycobilimbia lurida*
Lecidea macrocarpa (DC.) Steud. = *Porpidia macrocarpa*
Lecidea meiospora (Nyl.) Nyl. = *Porpidia cinereoatra*
Lecidea minuta (Schaer.) A. Massal. = *Lecania hyalina*
Lecidea musiva Körb. = *Porpidia musiva*
Lecidea olivacea (Hoffm.) A. Massal. = *Lecidella elaeochroma*
Lecidea pantherina (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Lecidella lapicida*
Lecidea parasema auct. = *Lecidella elaeochroma*
Lecidea platycarpa Ach. = *Porpidia macrocarpa*
Lecidea stigmatea Ach. = *Lecidella stigmatea*
Lecidea testacea (Hoffm.) Ach. = *Psora testacea*
Lecidea vulgata Zahlbr. = *Lecidella stigmatea*
- Lecidella enteroleuca* (Ach.) Körb. = *Lecidella elaeochroma*
Lecidella latypaea auct. = *Lecidella carpathica*
Lecidella pantherina (Ach.) Stein = *Lecidea lapicida*
Lecidella sudetica (Körb.) Stein = *Lecidea sudetica*
- Lempholemma fasciculare* (Wulf.) Zahlr. = *Lempholemma polyanthes*
Lempholemma myriococcum (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Lempholemma polyanthes*
- Lepraria candelaris* (L.) Fr. = *Chrysothrix candelaris*
- Leproloma membranaceum* (Dicks.) J.R. Laundon = *Lepraria membranacea*
- Leptogium lacerum* (Retz.) Gray = *Leptogium lichenoides*
Leptogium pulvinatum (Hoffm.) Cromb. = *Leptogium lichenoides*
- Letharia divaricata* (L.) Hue = *Evernia divaricata*
- Limboria actinostoma* (Ach.) A. Massal. = *Diploschistes actinostomus*
- Lithographa flexella* (Ach.) Zahlbr. = *Elixia flexella*
- Melanelia acetabulum* (Neck.) Essl. = *Pleurosticta acetabulum*
Melanelia glabratula (Lamy) Essl. = *Melanelia fuliginosa* subsp. *glabratula*
Melanelia solediosa (Almb.) Essl. = *Melanelia solediosa*
- Mycobilimbia sabuletorum* (Schreb.) Hafellner = *Myxobilimbia sabuletorum*
- Mycopyrenula coryli* (A. Massal.) Vain. = *Pyrenula coryli*
- Nephroma laevigatum* auct. = *Nephroma bellum*
- Nephromium tomentosum* (Hoffm.) Nyl. = *Nephroma resupinatum*
- Opegrapha diapora* Ach. = *Opegrapha varia*
Opegrapha grumulosa Dufour = *Lecanographa grumulosa*
Opegrapha herpetica (Ach.) Ach. = *Opegrapha rufescens*
Opegrapha lichenoides Pers. = *Opegrapha varia*
- Pachyospora verrucosa* (Ach.) A. Massal. = *Megaspora verrucosa*
- Pannaria brunnea* (Sw.) A. Massal. = *Protopannaria pezizoides*
Pannaria lanuginosa sensu Szatala = *Pannaria conoplea*
Pannaria nebulosa (Hoffm.) Nyl. = *Moelleropsis nebulosa*
Pannaria pezizoides (Weber) Trevis. = *Protopannaria pezizoides*
Pannaria saubinetii (Mont.) Nyl. = *Fuscopannaria saubinetii*
- Parmelia acetabulum* (Neck.) Duby = *Pleurosticta acetabulum*
Parmelia aspera A. Massal. = *Melanelia exasperata*
Parmelia aspidota (Ach.) Poetsch = *Melanelia exasperata*
Parmelia borveri auct. = *Punctelia subrudecta*
Parmelia caperata (L.) Ach. = *Flavoparmelia caperata*
Parmelia cetrarioides (Delise ex Duby) Nyl. = *Cetrelia cetrarioides*
Parmelia conspersa (Ehrh. ex Ach.) Ach. = *Xanthoparmelia conspersa*
Parmelia conspersa f. *hypoclista* Nyl. = *Xanthoparmelia sublaevis*
Parmelia cylisphora (Ach.) Vain. = *Flavoparmelia caperata*
Parmelia dubia (Wulfen) Schaer. = *Punctelia subrudecta*
Parmelia elegantula (Zahlbr.) Szatala = *Melanelia elegantula*
Parmelia exasperata De Not. = *Melanelia exasperata*
Parmelia exasperatula Nyl. = *Melanelia exasperatula*

- Parmelia fuliginosa* (Duby) Nyl. = *Melanelia fuliginosa* subsp. *fuliginosa*
Parmelia fuliginosa var. *laetevirens* (Flot.) F. Rosend. = *Melanelia fuliginosa* subsp. *glabratula*
Parmelia furfuracea (L.) Ach. = *Pseudevernia furfuracea*
Parmelia glabra (Schaer.) Nyl. = *Melanelia glabra*
Parmelia glabratula Lamy = *Melanelia fuliginosa* subsp. *glabratula*
Parmelia isidiata (Anzi) Gyeln. = *Xanthoparmelia conspersa*
Parmelia isidiotyta Nyl. = *Neofuscelia loxodes*
Parmelia laetevirens (Flot. ex Körb.) F. Rosend., nom. illeg. = *Melanelia fuliginosa* subsp. *glabratula*
Parmelia molliuscula auct. = *Xanthoparmelia somloënsis*
Parmelia olivacea (L.) Ach. = *Melanelia olivacea*
Parmelia olivaria (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Cetrelia olivetorum*
Parmelia pastillifera (Harm.) R. Schub. & Klem. = *Parmelina pastillifera*
Parmelia perlata Ach. = *Parmotrema chinense*
Parmelia physodes (L.) Ach. = *Hypogymnia physodes*
Parmelia proluxa (Ach.) Carroll = *Neofuscelia pulla*
Parmelia pulla Ach. = *Neofuscelia pulla*
Parmelia quercina (Willd.) Vain. = *Parmelina quercina*
Parmelia scortea (Ach.) Ach. = *Parmelina tiliacea*
Parmelia soreliata (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Melanelia soreliata*
Parmelia subargentifera Nyl. = *Melanelia subargentifera*
Parmelia subaurifera Nyl. = *Melanelia subaurifera*
Parmelia subrudecta Nyl. = *Punctelia subrudecta*
Parmelia tiliacea (Hoffm.) Ach. = *Parmelina tiliacea*
Parmelia trichotera Hue = *Parmotrema chinense*
Parmelia tubulosa (Schaer.) Bitter = *Hypogymnia tubulosa*
Parmelia verruculifera auct. = *Melanelia subargentifera*
Parmelia vittata (Ach.) Nyl. = *Hypogymnia vittata*
- Parmeliella saubinetii* (Mont.) Zahlbr. = *Fuscopannaria saubinetii*
- Parmeliopsis aleurites* (Ach.) Nyl. = *Imshaugia aleurites*
- Parmotrema perlatum* (Eschw.) M. Choisy = *Parmotrema chinense*
- Peltigera canina* f. *ulorrhiza* (Flörke) Schaer. = *Peltigera rufescens*
Peltigera spuria (Ach.) DC. = *Peltigera didactyla*
- Pertusaria communis* DC. = *Pertusaria pertusa*
Pertusaria communis var. *variolosa* (Flot.) Schaer. = *Pertusaria albescens*
Pertusaria discoidea (Pers.) Malme = *Pertusaria albescens*
Pertusaria faginea (L.) Vain. = *Pertusaria amara*
Pertusaria globulifera (Turner) A. Massal. = *Pertusaria albescens*
Pertusaria henrici sensu Erichsen = *Pertusaria albescens*
Pertusaria henrici var. *pallescens* Erichsen = *Ochrolechia turneri*
Pertusaria isidioides (Schaer.) Arnold = *Pertusaria schaeereri*
- Pertusaria laevigata* (Nyl.) Arnold = *Pertusaria trachyballina*
Pertusaria leptospora Nitschke ex J. Lahm = *Pertusaria multipuncta*
Pertusaria leucostoma A. Massal. = *Pertusaria leioplaca*
- Physcia adglutinata* (Flörke) Nyl. = *Hyperphyscia adglutinata*
Physcia cernohorskyi Nádv. = *Phaeophyscia cernohorskyi*
Physcia ciliata (Hoffm.) Moberg = *Phaeophyscia ciliata*
Physcia detersa (Nyl.) Nyl. = *Physconia detersa*
Physcia farrea auct. = *Physconia perisidiosa*
Physcia grisea (Lam.) Zahlbr. = *Physconia grisea*
Physcia grisea var. *detersa* (Nyl.) Lyngé = *Physconia detersa*
Physcia hispida (Schreb.) Mereschk. = *Physcia adscendens*
Physcia luganensis Mereschk. = *Phaeophyscia chloantha*
Physcia nigricans (Flörke) Stizenb. = *Phaeophyscia nigricans*
Physcia obscura auct. = *Phaeophyscia ciliata*
Physcia obscura var. *ciliata* (Hoffm.) Tuck. = *Phaeophyscia ciliata*
Physcia orbicularis (Neck.) Poetsch. = *Phaeophyscia orbicularis*
Physcia pulverulenta ("Hoffm.") Fürnr. = *Physconia distorta*
Physcia pulverulenta var. *venusta* (Ach.) Nyl. = *Physconia venusta*
Physcia sciastra (Ach.) Du Rietz = *Phaeophyscia sciastra*
Physcia sciastrella (Nyl.) Harm. = *Phaeophyscia nigricans*
Physcia venusta (Ach.) Nyl. = *Physconia venusta*
Physcia virella (Ach.) Flagey = *Phaeophyscia orbicularis*
Physcia wainioi Räsänen = *Physcia caesia*
- Physciopsis adglutinata* (Flörke) M. Choisy = *Hyperphyscia adglutinata*
- Placidiopsis tatrensis* Vězda = *Placopyrenium tatrense*
- Placodium murorum* (Hoffm.) DC. = *Caloplaca saxicola*
Placodium saxiculum (Pollich) Frege = *Protoparmeliopsis muralis*
Placodium subcircinatum (Nyl.) Arnold = *Lobothallia radiosa*
- Polyblastia abstrahenda* Arnold = *Polyblastia fuscoargillacea*
Polyblastia gelatinosa (Ach.) Th. Fr. = *Agonimia gelatinosa*
- Polyblastiopsis fallaciosa* (Stizenb. ex Arnold) Zahlbr. = *Julella fallaciosa*
- Porina aenea* (Wallr.) Zahlbr. = *Pseudosagedia aenea*
Porina carpinea (Pers. ex Ach.) Zahlbr. = *Pseudosagedia aenea*
Porina chlorotica var. *carpinea* (Ach.) Keissl. = *Pseudosagedia aenea*
- Protoblastenia immersa* (Hoffm.) Hafellner & Bellem. = *Clauzadea immersa*
Protoblastenia monticola (Schaer.) J. Steiner = *Clauzadea monticola*

- Protoblastenia testacea* (Hoffm.) Clauzade & Rondon = *Psora testacea*
- Psora albilabra* auct. = *Psora vallesiaca*
- Pyrenula nitida* var. *nitidella* (Schaer.) Schaer. = *Pyrenula nitidella*
- Ramalina baltica* Lettau = *Ramalina obtusata*
Ramalina intermedia auct. = *Ramalina pollinaria*
Ramalina strepsilis (Ach.) Zahlbr. = *Ramalina capitata*
- Rhizocarpon ambiguum* (Schaer.) Zahlbr. = *Rhizocarpon distinctum*
Rhizocarpon atrovirens auct. = *Rhizocarpon lecanorinum*
Rhizocarpon calcareum (Ach.) Anzi = *Rhizocarpon umbilicatum*
Rhizocarpon concentricum auct. = *Rhizocarpon petraeum*
Rhizocarpon montagnei Körb. = *Rhizocarpon disporum*
- Rinodina bischoffii* var. *immersa* Körb. = *Rinodina immersa*
Rinodina crustulata (A. Massal.) Arnold = *Rinodinella controversa*
Rinodina discolor (Hepp) Arnold = *Rinodina oxydata*
Rinodina mediterranea (Stizenb.) Flagey = *Rinodina dubyana*
Rinodina ocellata (Hoffm.) Arnold = *Rinodina lecanorina*
Rinodina salina Degel. = *Rinodina gennarii*
Rinodina serpentinei H. Mayrhofer & Poelt = *Rinodina rinodinooides*
- Sarcogyne pruinosa* auct. = *Sarcogyne regularis*
Sarcogyne simplex (Davies) Nyl. = *Polysporina simplex*
- Sphaerophorus coralloides* Pers. = *Sphaerophorus globosus*
- Squamarina crassa* (Huds.) Poelt = *Squamarina cartilaginea*
- Staurothele catalepta* auct. = *Staurothele frustulenta*
- Sticta pulmonaria* (L.) Biroli = *Lobaria pulmonaria*
- Synechoblastus flaccidus* (Ach.) Körb. = *Collema flaccidum*
- Thalloidima vesiculare* (Hoffm.) Boistel = *Toninia sedifolia*
- Thyrea pulvinata* auct. = *Thyrea confusa*
- Toninia caeruleonigricans* auct. = *Toninia sedifolia*
Toninia intermedia (A. Massal. ex Arnold) H. Olivier = *Toninia alutacea*
Toninia lobulata (Sommerf.) Lyngby = *Myxobilimbia lobulata*
Toninia mesenteriforme (Vill.) H. Olivier = *Toninia tumidula*
Toninia zsakii (Szat.) Lettau = *Micarea melaenida*
- Umbilicaria pustulata* (L.) Hoffm. = *Lasallia pustulata*
- Urceolaria ocellata* (Vill.) DC. = *Diploschistes ocellatus*
Urceolaria scruposa L. = *Diploschistes scruposus*
Urceolaria scruposa f. *musciicola* Anzi = *Diploschistes muscorum*
- Usnea dasypoga* auct. = *Usnea filipendula*
Usnea florida (L.) Weber ex F.H. Wigg. = *Usnea subfloridana*
- Verrucaria arnoldii* J. Steiner = *Verrucaria hochstetteri*
Verrucaria baldensis A. Massal. = *Bagliettoa baldensis*
Verrucaria baldensis var. *serbica* (Servit) Servit = *Bagliettoa baldensis*
Verrucaria controversa A. Massal. = *Verrucaria nigrescens*
Verrucaria denudata Zschacke = *Verrucaria hydrela*
Verrucaria fusca auct. = *Verrucaria nigrescens*
Verrucaria glaucina Ach. = *Verrucaria caerulea*
Verrucaria griseoatra (Kremp.) Servit = *Verrucaria fuscella*
Verrucaria nigricans Nyl. = *Verrucaria fuscella*
Verrucaria parmigera J. Steiner = *Bagliettoa parmigera*
Verrucaria parmigerella Zahlbr. = *Bagliettoa parmigerella*
Verrucaria rupestris Schrad. non (Scop.) F.H. Wigg. = *Verrucaria muralis*
Verrucaria serbica Servit = *Bagliettoa baldensis*
Verrucaria sphinctrina auct. = *Verrucaria limborioides*
Verrucaria steineri Kušan = *Bagliettoa steineri*
- Xanthocarpia ochracea* (Schaer.) A. Massal. = *Caloplaca ochracea*
- Xanthoria aureola* auct. = *Xanthoria calcicola*
Xanthoria lobulata (Flörke) de Lesd. = *Caloplaca lobulata*
- Xylographa abietina* (Pers.) Zahlbr. = *Xylographa parallela*
- Zeora sordida* (Pers.) Körb. = *Lecanora rupicola*

Doubtful names and excluded records:

- Arthonia cytisi* A. Massal. (Servit 1934: 126; Kušan 1953: 108; Murati 1992: 86)
- Aspicilia crusii* Klem. (Krause & Klement 1958: 6)
- Bilimbia sphaeroides* Sommerf. (Simić 1895: 130)
- Caloplaca arenaria* (Pers.) Müll. Arg. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175; Kušan 1953: 502; Murati 1993: 85). These records may refer to either *C. erythrocarpa* (Pers.) Zwackh or *C. teicholyta* (Ach.) J. Steiner.
- Caloplaca ferruginea* var. *saxicola* (A. Massal.) J. Steiner (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175)
- Caloplaca incrustans* (Ach.) Decuill. (Gallé 1975: 294)
- Dermatocarpon glaucinum* (Krause & Klement 1958: 7)
- Dermatocarpon subfuscillum* (Krause & Klement 1958: 7)
- Lecanora platycarpa* f. *pruinosa* J. Steiner (Servit 1935: 79; Kušan 1953: 366)

- Lecanora pleiospora* var. *zimmermanni* Servít. (Servít 1935: 79; Kušan 1953: 388)
- Lecanora subfusca* (this name has been used for a complex of species including e.g. *Lecanora allophana*, *L. rugosella*, etc. (Simić 1892: 452, 1895: 125 & 147, 1897: 7, 1900: 47; Katić 1910: 40; Szatala & Timkó 1926: 168; Soška 1949: 110; Kušan 1953: 393; Murati 1993: 147; Cvijan *et al.* 1995: 178; Dimović 2003: 145)
- Lecidea convexa* (Murati 1992: 309 as '*Porpidia musiva* = *Lecidea convexa*')
- Lecidea enteroleuca* Ach. (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 164)
- Lecidea pachyphloea* Körb. (Katić 1907: 14)
- Parmelia mitrovicensis* Gyeln. (Gyelnik 1932b: 488)
- Parmelia serbica* Gyeln. (Gyelnik 1932b: 488)
- Pertusaria henrici* var. *granosa* Erichs. (Gallé 1975: 292)
- Physcia obscura* Ehrh. (Gallé 1935: 272)
- Physcia obscura* Ehrh. (Simić 1895: 122)
- Rinodina laevigata* (Ach.) Malme (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 177; Servít 1935: 85)
- Rinodina metabolica* α *exigua* A. Massal. (Simić 1892: 451)
- Usnea albanica* Bystrek & Murati (Murati 1993: 243, *nomen nudum*)
- Usnea florida* var. *sorediifera* Arnold (Szatala & Timkó 1926: 175)
- Verrucaria calciseda* f. *calcivora* A. Massal. (Servít 1935: 73; Kušan 1953: 26)
- Verrucaria pinguis* J. Steiner (Zschacke 1934: 87; Kušan 1953: 26)

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